

Jean Monnet Chair

for EU's Circular Economy Policies and Sustainability (CESPEU)

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Editors

Betül GÜR
Elçin AYKAÇ ALP
Sabri ÖZ

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CONTENT / İÇİNDEKİLER

FOREWORD / ÖNSÖZ	5
SCIENTIFIC COMMITTEE (Alphabetical)	7
PROGRAM SCHEDULE	8
SESSION 1 SCHEDULE	8
SESSION 2 SCHEDULE	9
SESSION 3 SCHEDULE	10
SESSION 4 SCHEDULE	11
OPENING SPEECH	12
PROF. DR. SERKAN ÇANKAYA	14
PROF. DR. BETÜL GÜR	16
KEYNOTE SPEECH	17
PROF. FRANCO MOSCONI	18
PROF. DR. MURAT ALİ YÜLEK	19
DR. ARMAĞAN VURDU	20
SESSION 1 PRESENTATIONS – Moderated by İlker KÖSE, PhD	23
Necla İLTER KÜÇÜKÇOLAK, Assoc. Prof., Turkish Merchantile Exchange	23
Designing Climate-Smart Sustainable Agricultural Markets: Legal Alignment of Türkiye’s Climate Law with the EU and a Carbon Market Instrument Proposal for Agricultural Commodities	23
Bura Sabiha KELEK, Assist. Prof., İstanbul Medipol University	25
The Relationship and Impact of Circular Economy and Sustainability Concepts with the Aviation Industry	25
Yusuf GÜNGÖR, PhD (c), İstanbul Ticaret University	26
Ayben KOY, Assoc. Prof., İstanbul Ticaret University	26
Gender on Board: How Female Representation Strengthens Governance and Profitability	26
Şüheda BARAN SATILMIŞ, PhD. İstanbul Ticaret University	27
Mapping The Evolution of Circular Economy and Sustainability Research	27

Tolga ERKAN, Assoc. Prof., OSTİM Technical University Faculty	28
Bahattin Gökhan TOPAL, Coordinator, Technology Transfer Office, OSTİM Technical University Faculty	28
Green Cities and Urban Biodiversity	28
SESSION 2 PRESENTATIONS – Moderated by Elçin AYKAÇ ALP, Prof. Dr.....	30
M. Towsif HASAN, Professor, Melbourne University, Australia	30
Closing the Loop: A Digital Twin Framework for Whole-Life Carbon Optimization	30
Ayben KOY, Professor, İstanbul Ticaret University	32
Semra DEMİR, Assist. Prof., Burdur Mehmet Akif Ersoy University	32
Modeling the Dynamics of Sustainable Finance: A Nonlinear Approach to Borsa Istanbul Sustainability Indices.....	32
Recep Ali KÜÇÜKÇOLAK, Assoc. Prof., İstanbul Ticaret University	33
Effects of the New Climate Law on Financial Markets in Türkiye.....	33
Abdul Baghi NABIYEV, İstanbul School of Technology, Azerbaijan.....	34
Sustainable and Climate Finance within the Framework of the Circular Economy: Challenges and Opportunities for Central Banks	34
SESSION 3 PRESENTATIONS – Moderated by Sabri ÖZ, Assoc. Prof. Dr.	35
Gizem ATEŞ, Ph.D., Research Assist., İnönü University	35
Beyhan MARŞAP, Prof., Ankara Hacı Bayram Veli University	35
Devrim HULTEN, Assoc. Prof., Lund University, Sweden	35
Circular Economy Policies and Sustainable Innovation in the Construction Sector: Sweden and Türkiye Scoping Study	35
Azmi STRINGA, PhD (c), University of Tirana, Albania	37
Manjola NACO, Assist., Prof., Metropolitan University Tirana, Albania.....	37
Alban KORBI, Assist. Prof., University of Tirana, Albania.....	37
From Growth to Sustainability: Rethinking Albania’s Economy for Inclusive and Sustainable Development.....	37
Alara SAYGI, Researcher, European Relations Club.....	39
Sergen GAYRETLİ, Researcher, European Relations Club	39
Pathways to Modernisation CBAM’s Role in Transforming the Türkiye-EU Customs Union	39
Akif Emrah BÜYÜKSOMER, PhD C.	40
Federated Learning in the Circular Economy: A Systematic Literature Review	40

Müge ÖZ, Int. Industrialists' and Businesswomen's Association (USIKAD) Chair Holder	41
Bekir Berat Yalın EKER, Adv., İstanbul School of Technology	41
Sabri ÖZ, Assoc. Prof., BeTa Science Association, İstanbul School of Technology	41
Public Relations Evaluation of the Climate Law in Turkey: A Qualitative Analysis, to be Aside or Not!	41
Adem KAYAR, PhD, Digital and Sustainable Future Association, Chairman of the Board	42
The Impact of Digital Transformation in Industry on Circular Economy and Carbon Footprint Reduction in the Manufacturing Sector.....	42
SESSION 4 PRESENTATION – Moderated by Betül GÜR, Prof. Dr.	44
Serap ÖZTÜRK, Manager, Republic of Türkiye Ministry of Agriculture and Forestry, İstanbul/Beyoğlu District Directorate of Agriculture and Forestry,.....	44
İstanbul/Beyoğlu İlçesi Sürdürülebilirlik Çalışmaları: İyi Uygulama Örnekleri / İstanbul/Beyoğlu District Sustainability Studies: Good Practice Examples.....	44
Müge KOÇUM SEVİM, PhD, Visiting Lecturer, İstinye University	46
Figen YAVUZ, Assist. Prof., İstanbul Nişantaşı University	46
Tekstil Sektöründe Döngüsel Ekonomi Yaklaşımları: Uygulamalar, Zorluklar ve Gelecek Perspektifleri / Circular Economy Approaches in the Textile Sector: Applications, Challenges and Future Perspectives.....	46
Selda ERDOĞAN, PhD (c), Lecturer, İstanbul Medipol University.....	48
Cihat KÖKSAL, Assoc. Prof. İstanbul Ticaret University	48
Karbon Salınımı ve Ekolojik Ayak İzinin Uluslararası Ticarete Etkisi: Tekstil Sektörü Örneği / The Effect of Carbon Emission and Ecological Footprint on International Trade: The Case of Textile Sector.....	48
Rana Yaren ÖZLÜK, Independent Researcher, Türkiye.....	49
Döngüsel Ekonomiye Geçişte Türkiye Tekstil Sektörü Uygulamaları / Turkish Textile Sector Practices in Transition to Circular Economy	49
Mehmet DUMAN, Independent Researcher, Türkiye.....	50
Türkiye'de Kamu Gözetimi Kurumunun Sürdürülebilirlik Politikaları Üzerindeki Etkisi / The Impact of Public Oversight on Sustainability Policies in Türkiye	50
CLOSING STATEMENT – Declared by Prof. Dr. Betül GÜR, Chair Holder	52

FOREWORD / ÖNSÖZ

Döngüsel Ekonomi Politikaları ve Sürdürülebilirlik Jean Monnet Kürsümüzün, kapanış etkinliğini gerçekleştirmek üzere Final Konferansı düzenledik. Her zamanki gibi güzel bir katılımcı grubu bizi yalnız bırakmadı. Birbirinden kıymetli sunumlar dinledik. Birbirinden kıymetli katılımcılarımız ilgiyle oturumları takip etti. Üç yıllık bir projeksiyonda, yüzlerce katılımcının fiilen dahil olduğu, iş dünyasından sivil toplum kuruluşlarından, reel sektörlerden ve akademiden temsilciler için oldukça yoğun programlar etkinlikler gerçekleştirdik. Her ne kadar Jean Monnet Kürsüsünün sonunda olsak da, aslında döngüsellik ve sürdürülebilirlik konularına duyulan ilgili giderek arttığına şahit olduk. Bu proje ile, döngüsel ekonomi ve sürdürülebilirlik hususunda farkındalığın artması için bir taş da biz koymuş olduk. İktisadi, siyasi, toplumsal hayata ilişkin, bilim dünyasının her alanında bu konuda akademik çalışmalar, projeler yapılmakta ve zengin bir literatür oluşumuna destek vermiş olduk. Günümüzde küresel ekonominin ve siyasetin dönüşüm süreci içinde yeni güçlerin ortaya çıkması, döngüsel ekonomi ve sürdürülebilirlik politikalarının önemini daha da vurgulamaktadır. AB'nin sürdürülebilir ve döngüsel ekonomi ilkeleri çerçevesinde üretim ve ihracat yapmaya yönelik politikaları gerek küresel üretim ve ticareti, gerekse kendisine rakip yükselen yeni ekonomileri iktisadi ve siyasi olarak yeni stratejiler üretmeye itmektedir. Dolayısıyla döngüsel ekonomi ve sürdürülebilirlik politikaları geleceğin ekonomik ve çevresel zeminini belirleyen önemli birer unsur olarak karşımıza çıkmaktadır.

We held the Final Conference to mark the closing event of our Jean Monnet Chair in Circular Economy Policies and Sustainability. As always, we were met with a wonderful group of participants. We listened to a variety of valuable presentations, and our esteemed participants followed the sessions with great interest. Over the three-year period, we organized a series of intense programs and events for representatives from the business world, civil society organizations, the real sector, and academia, with hundreds of participants participating. Although we are currently at the end of the Jean Monnet Chair, we have witnessed a growing interest in circularity and sustainability. With this project, we have laid a foundation for raising awareness of the circular economy and sustainability. Academic studies and projects are being conducted on this topic in every field of economics, politics, social life, and the scientific world, and we have supported the creation of a rich literature. The emergence of new forces within the current transformation of the global economy and politics further underscores the importance of circular economy and sustainability policies. The EU's policies for production and exports, within the framework of sustainable and circular economy principles, are pushing both global production and trade, as well as emerging rival economies, to develop new economic and political strategies. Therefore, circular economy and sustainability policies emerge as important elements shaping the economic and environmental landscape of the future.

Jean Monnet öncelikle bir ders verme, bir eğitim-öğretim faaliyetidir. Biz de bu çerçevede ilk olarak dersler ve tezlerle başladık. Üç yıl boyunca her sene kürsü hocaları olarak Prof. Dr. Betül Gür, Prof. Dr. Elçin Aykaç Alp ve Doç. Dr. Sabri Öz tarafından; Avrupa Ekonomik Entegrasyonu, Sanayi Politikaları, İleri Sanayi Politikaları, Seminer, Çok Taraflı Ticaret Sistemi, Döngüsel Ekonomi ve Sürdürülebilirlik derslerini, lisans, yüksek lisans ve doktora düzeyinde, hem Türkçe hem de İngilizce olarak yaklaşık 330 öğrenciye dersler verildi.

Dolayısıyla Jean Monnet Kürsüsü olarak lisans, yüksek lisans ve doktora derslerimizle, tamamlanmış ve tamamlanmak üzere olan 30'a yakın yüksek lisans ve doktora tezleri ve bir o kadar Lisansüstü öğrencileri makale çalışmalarlarıyla kürsü önemli akademik misyonunu yerine getirmeye gayret etmiştir. Bunların yanısıra lisansüstü öğrencileri ve konuyla ilgilenen yurtiçi ve yurt dışından birçok araştırmacı ve akademisyenle birlikte yazılan 21 bölümlük, yaklaşık 800 sayfadan oluşan "Sürdürülebilirlik ve Döngüsel Ekonomi" adlı eser kürsünün önemli çıktıları arasındadır. Kürsünün, web sayfası ve sosyal medya mecralarında bültenler, etkinlik paylaşımları, gazeteler, sertifikalı kış okulu yaz okulu etkinlikleri, seminerler, çalıştaylar geeniş yankı uyandırmıştır.

Nihai olarak bu konferans ile, önemli keynote konuşmaları ardından seçilmiş 20 adet bildiri sunumları gerçekleştirildi ve bu proceeding dahilinde yayınlanmaktadır. bu bildirimler tam metin haline dönüşenler için uluslararası hakemli dergilerde yayınlanmak üzere çalışmalar sürüyor.

Çalışmanın toplumsal fayda sağlaması sevinci ve haklı gururu ile saygılar sunarız.

Editörler

Jean Monnet is primarily a teaching and educational activity. We began with courses and theses within this framework. For three years, the department's instructors, Prof. Dr. Betül Gür, Prof. Dr. Elçin Aykaç Alp, and Assoc. Prof. Dr. Sabri Öz, taught European Economic Integration, Industrial Policies, Advanced Industrial Policies, Seminars, the Multilateral Trading System, Circular Economy, and Sustainability courses to approximately 330 students at the undergraduate, graduate, and doctoral levels, in both Turkish and English.

Therefore, as the Jean Monnet Chair, the chair has strived to fulfill its important academic mission through our undergraduate, graduate, and doctoral courses, nearly 30 completed and nearing completion master's and doctoral theses, and a similar number of articles by graduate students. In addition, the 21-chapter, approximately 800-page work titled "Sustainability and the Circular Economy," written in collaboration with graduate students and numerous domestic and international researchers and academics interested in the subject, is among the chair's significant outputs. Bulletins, event posts, newspapers, certified winter and summer school events, seminars, and workshops have generated widespread interest on the chair's website and social media platforms.

Finally, this conference following important keynote speeches, featured presentations of 20 selected papers, which are being published as part of this proceeding. Efforts are underway to publish these full-text papers in internationally peer-reviewed journals.

We offer our respects with the joy and justified pride that the fruitfulness of this work has translated into social benefit.

Editors

SCIENTIFIC COMMITTEE (Alphabetical)

Abdul Baghi NABIEV, <i>PhD</i>	İstanbul School of Technology, AZERBAIJAN
Ahmet ÖZEMRE, <i>PhD</i>	Universidade NOVA de Lisboa, PORTUGAL
Ardita BYLO, <i>PhD</i>	New York Tirana University, ALBANIA
Ayben KOY, <i>Professor</i>	İstanbul Ticaret University, TÜRKİYE
Betül GÜR, <i>Professor</i>	İstanbul Ticaret University, TÜRKİYE
Bhushan Namdeorao YENGADE, <i>Professor</i>	Ministry of Agriculture & Farmers Welfare, INDIA
Bura Sabiha KELEK, <i>PhD</i>	İstanbul Medipol University, TÜRKİYE
Çiğdem ÜSTÜN, <i>Professor</i>	İstanbul Nişantaşı University, TÜRKİYE
Elçin AYKAÇ ALP, <i>Professor</i>	İstanbul Ticaret University, TÜRKİYE
Elif GÜNEREN GENÇ, <i>Professor</i>	İstanbul Ticaret University, TÜRKİYE
Fatma Serap ONURSAL, <i>Assoc. Professor</i>	İstanbul Medipol University, TÜRKİYE
Franco MOSCONI, <i>Professor</i>	Università studi di Parma, ITALY
Grzegorz ZAJAC, <i>PhD</i>	Old Polish University, POLAND
Murat Adil SALEPÇİOĞLU, <i>PhD</i>	İstanbul Aydın University, TÜRKİYE
Murat AKKAYA, <i>Professor</i>	İstanbul Beykent University, TÜRKİYE
Murat Ali YÜLEK, <i>Professor</i>	OSTİM Technical University, TÜRKİYE
Necdet ŞENSOY, <i>Professor</i>	İstanbul Ticaret University, TÜRKİYE
Sabri ÖZ, <i>Assoc. Professor</i>	İstanbul Ticaret University, TÜRKİYE
Serkan ÇANKAYA, <i>Professor</i>	İstanbul Ticaret University, TÜRKİYE
Seyhun DOĞAN, <i>Professor</i>	İstanbul University, TÜRKİYE
Tunç DURMAZ, <i>Assoc. Professor</i>	Yıldız Technical Üniversitesi, TÜRKİYE

PROGRAM SCHEDULE

OPENING SPEECHES

10:00-10:15

Serkan ÇANKAYA

Professor, İstanbul Ticaret University, Rector Counsellor

Betül GÜR

Professor, İstanbul Ticaret University, Jean Monnet Chair for CESPEU Chair Holder

KEYNOTE SPEAKERS

10:15-10:30

Franco MOSCONI

Professor, Università di Parma

10:30-10:45

Murat Ali YÜLEK

Professor, OSTİM Technical University, Rector

10:45-11:00

S. Armağan VURDU

PhD, General Secretary of the İstanbul Mineral and Metals Exporters' Association

SESSION 1 SCHEDULE

1 ST SESSION / 11:00-12:30	
Moderator: İlker KÖSE PhD, İstanbul Ticaret Uni. Technology Transfer Office, Coordinator	
11:00-11:15	Necla İLTER KÜÇÜKÇOLAK , <i>Assoc. Prof., Turkish Merchantile Exchange</i> “Designing Climate-Smart Sustainable Agricultural Markets: Legal Alignment of Türkiye’s Climate Law with the EU and a Carbon Market Instrument Proposal for Agricultural Commodities”
11:15-11:30	Bura Sabiha KELEK , <i>Assist. Prof., İstanbul Medipol University</i> “The Relationship and Impact of Circular Economy and Sustainability Concepts with the Aviation Industry”
11:30-11:45	Yusuf GÜNGÖR , <i>PhD (c), İstanbul Ticaret University</i> Ayben KOY , <i>Assoc. Prof., İstanbul Ticaret University</i> “Gender on Board: How Female Representation Strengthens Governance and Profitability”
11:45-12:00	Şüheda BARAN SATILMIŞ , <i>PhD, İstanbul Ticaret University</i> “Mapping The Evolution of Circular Economy and Sustainability Research”
12:00-12:15	Tolga ERKAN , <i>Assoc. Prof., OSTİM Technical University Faculty</i> Bahattin Gökhan TOPAL , <i>Coordinator, Technology Transfer Office, OSTİM Technical University Faculty</i> “Green Cities and Urban Biodiversity”
Q-A	

SESSION 2 SCHEDULE

2ND SESSION / 12:30-14:00	
Moderator: Elçin AYKAÇ ALP Professor, Jean Monnet Chair for CESPEU, Chair Member	
12:30-12:45	M. Towsif HASAN , <i>Professor, Melbourne University, Australia</i> “Closing the Loop: A Digital Twin Framework for Whole-Life Carbon Optimization”
13:00-13:15	Ayben KOY , <i>Professor, İstanbul Ticaret University</i> Semra DEMİR , <i>Assist. Prof., Burdur Mehmet Akif Ersoy University</i> “Modeling the Dynamics of Sustainable Finance: A Nonlinear Approach to Borsa Istanbul Sustainability Indices”
13:15-13:30	Recep Ali KÜÇÜKÇOLAK , <i>Assoc. Prof., İstanbul Ticaret University</i> “Effects of the New Climate Law on Financial Markets in Türkiye”
13:30-13:45	Abdul Baghi NABIYEV , <i>İstanbul School of Technology, Azerbaijan</i> “Sustainable and Climate Finance within the Framework of the Circular Economy: Challenges and Opportunities for Central Banks”
Q-A	

SESSION 3 SCHEDULE

3RD SESSION / 14:00-15:30	
MODERATOR: Sabri ÖZ Assoc. Professor, Jean Monnet Chair for CESPEU, Chair Member	
14:00-14:15	Gizem ATEŞ , <i>Ph.D., Research Assist., İnönü University</i> Beyhan MARŞAP , <i>Professor, Ankara Hacı Bayram Veli University</i> Devrim HULTEN , <i>Assoc. Professor, Lund University, Sweden</i> “Circular Economy Policies and Sustainable Innovation in the Construction Sector: Sweden and Türkiye Scoping Study”
14:15-14:30	Azmi STRINGA , <i>PhD (c), University of Tirana, Albania</i> Manjola NACO , <i>Assist., Prof., Metropolitan University Tirana, Albania</i> Alban KORBI , <i>Assist. Prof., University of Tirana, Albania</i> “From Growth to Sustainability: Rethinking Albania’s Economy for Inclusive and Sustainable Development”
14:30-14:45	Alara SAYGI , <i>Researcher, European Relations Club</i> Sergen GAYRETLİ , <i>Researcher, European Relations Club</i> “Pathways to Modernisation CBAM’s Role in Transforming the Türkiye-EU Customs Union”
14:45-15:00	Akif Emrah BÜYÜKSOMER, PhD C. “Federated Learning in the Circular Economy: A Systematic Literature Review”
15:00-15:15	Müge ÖZ , <i>Int. Industrialists' and Businesswomen's Association (USIKAD) Chair Holder</i> Bekir Berat Yalın EKER , <i>Advocate., İstanbul School of Technology</i> Sabri ÖZ , <i>Assoc. Prof. Dr. İstanbul School of Technology, BeTa Science Association</i> “Tekstil Sektöründe Döngüsel Ekonomi Yaklaşımları: Uygulamalar, Zorluklar ve Gelecek Perspektifleri / Public Relations Evaluation of the Climate Law in Türkiye: A Qualitative Analysis To be a Side or Not!”
15:15-15:30	Adem KAYAR , <i>PhD, Digital and Sustainable Future Association, Chairman of the Board</i> “Türkiye’de Kamu Gözetimi Kurumunun Sürdürülebilirlik Politikaları Üzerindeki Etkisi / The Impact of Digital Transformation in Industry on Circular Economy and Carbon Footprint Reduction in the Manufacturing Sector”
Q-A	

SESSION 4 SCHEDULE

4 TH SESSION / 15:30-17:15	
Moderator: Betül GÜR Professor, Jean Monnet Chair for CESPEU, Chair Holder	
15:30-15:45	Serap ÖZTÜRK , <i>Manager, Republic of Türkiye Ministry of Agriculture and Forestry, Istanbul/Beyoğlu District Directorate of Agriculture and Forestry,</i> “İstanbul/Beyoğlu İlçesi Sürdürülebilirlik Çalışmaları: İyi Uygulama Örnekleri / Istanbul/Beyoğlu District Sustainability Studies: Good Practice Examples”
16:00-16:15	Müge KOÇUM SEVİM , <i>PhD, Visiting Lecturer, İstinye University</i> Figen YAVUZ , <i>Assist. Prof., İstanbul Nişantaşı University</i> “Circular Economy Approaches in the Textile Sector: Applications, Challenges and Future Perspectives”
16:15-16:30	Selda ERDOĞAN , <i>PhD (c), Lecturer, İstanbul Medipol University</i> Cihat KÖKSAL , <i>Assoc. Prof. Dr., İstanbul Ticaret University</i> “The Effect of Carbon Emission and Ecological Footprint on International Trade: The Case of Textile Sector”
16:30-16:45	Rana Yaren ÖZLÜK , <i>Independent Researcher, Türkiye</i> “Döngüsel Ekonomiye Geçişte Türkiye Tekstil Sektörü Uygulamaları / Turkish Textile Sector Practices in Transition to Circular Economy”
16:45-17:00	Mehmet DUMAN , <i>Independent Researcher, Türkiye</i> “Türkiye’de Kamu Gözetimi Kurumunun Sürdürülebilirlik Politikaları Üzerindeki Etkisi”
Q-A	

CLOSING SPEECH

17:15-17:30

Betül GÜR

Professor, İstanbul Ticaret University, Jean Monnet Chair for CESPEU Chair Holder

OPENING SPEECH

Opening speeches are given by the İstanbul Ticaret University Rector Counsellor Prof. Dr. Serkan Çankaya and the Jean Monnet Chair Holder Prof. Dr. Betül Gür.

Prof. Franco Mosconi

Prof. Dr. Mustafa Yalçık

PROF. DR. SERKAN ÇANKAYA

Sayın katılımcılar, değerli meslektaşlarım
ve saygıdeğer konuklar,

AB'nin Döngüsel Ekonomi Politikaları ve Sürdürülebilirlik (CESPEU) Jean Monnet Kürsüsü'nün Son Konferansı'na hoş geldiniz demek benim için bir onur ve büyük bir zevktir. İstanbul Ticaret Üniversitesi Rektörü ve tüm akademik topluluğu adına, dünyanın çeşitli bölgelerinden bugün bu çevrimiçi ortamda bize katıldığımız için içtenlikle teşekkür ederim.

Bu konferans, Jean Monnet Kürsüsü çerçevesindeki işbirliği yolculuğumuzda önemli bir dönüm noktasıdır. Bu yolculuk, sürdürülebilirlik ve döngüsel ekonomi gibi kritik alanlarda araştırma, diyalog ve pratik çözümlerin geliştirilmesine adanmıştır. Bu alanlar, teorik kavramlardan, daha sürdürülebilir ve dayanıklı bir gelecek şekillendirmek için gerekli olan küresel eylemlere dönüşmüştür.

İstanbul Ticaret Üniversitesi'nde sürdürülebilirlik, kurumsal stratejimiz ve akademik çabalarımızın merkezinde yer almaktadır. CESPEU gibi girişimler aracılığıyla kurumumuz, yalnızca çağdaş Avrupa politika tartışmalarına derinlemesine katılmakla kalmayıp, aynı zamanda akademik görüşleri uygulanabilir politikalara ve somut sonuçlara dönüştürmeyi de amaçlamaktadır.

Profesör Betül Gür'ün seçkin liderliği altında, bu proje sürdürülebilirlik konusunda sağlam akademik alışverişleri, disiplinler arası işbirliğini ve yenilikçi yaklaşımları başarıyla teşvik etmiştir.

Distinguished participants, esteemed colleagues, and honoured guests,

It is my privilege and great pleasure to welcome you to the Final Conference of the Jean Monnet Chair for EU's Circular Economy Policies and Sustainability (CESPEU). On behalf of the Rector and the entire academic community of İstanbul Ticaret University, I sincerely thank you for joining us today from various regions across the globe in this online setting.

This conference marks an important milestone in our collaborative journey under the Jean Monnet Chair framework—a journey dedicated to advancing research, dialogue, and practical solutions within the critical fields of sustainability and circular economy. These areas have transitioned from theoretical concepts into necessary global actions, integral to shaping a more sustainable and resilient future.

At İstanbul Ticaret University, sustainability occupies a central place in our institutional strategy and academic endeavours. Through initiatives such as CESPEU, our institution seeks not only to engage deeply with contemporary European policy debates but also to translate scholarly insights into actionable policies and tangible outcomes. Under the distinguished leadership of Professor Betül Gür, this project has successfully fostered robust academic exchanges, interdisciplinary collaboration, and innovative approaches to sustainability.

Today's conference agenda underscores this multidisciplinary commitment by addressing diverse yet interconnected themes—including climate-smart agriculture, sustainable finance,

Bugünkü konferans gündemi, iklim dostu tarım, sürdürülebilir finans, yeşil şehirler, yönetişimde cinsiyet eşitliği, yapay zeka ve havacılık ve tekstil gibi endüstri sektörlerinde döngüsel uygulamalar gibi çeşitli ancak birbiriyle bağlantılı temaları ele alarak bu çok disiplinli taahhüdü vurgulamaktadır. Bu geniş konu yelpazesi, gerçek sürdürülebilirliği sağlamanın karmaşıklığını ve etkili, sistematik çözümler oluşturmak için çeşitli uzmanlıkların katılımının gerekliliğini vurgulamaktadır.

Bilimsel komite üyeleri, saygın ana konuşmacılarımız, panel moderatörleri ve sunumcularımıza, görüşleri ve katkılarıyla bugünkü diyalogu zenginleştirdikleri için içten teşekkürlerimizi sunarız. Kolektif uzmanlığınız, ortak anlayışımızı ve anlamlı bir etki yaratma kapasitemizi önemli ölçüde artırmaktadır.

Sanal olarak bir araya gelmiş olsak da, bu konferans sırasında geliştirilen entelektüel alışverişlerin ve profesyonel ağların ekranlarımızın ötesinde yankı bulacağına ve devam eden araştırma girişimlerini, politika gelişmelerini ve işbirliği ortaklıklarını katalize edeceğine inanıyorum.

Bir kez daha hoş geldiniz ve hepinize içgörülü, verimli ve ilham verici bir konferans diliyorum.

Teşekkür ederim.

green cities, gender equality in governance, artificial intelligence, and circular practices within industry sectors such as aviation and textiles. This breadth of topics emphasizes the complexity of achieving genuine sustainability and the necessity of engaging diverse expertise to build effective, systemic solutions.

We extend our sincere appreciation to the members of the scientific committee, our eminent keynote speakers, panel moderators, and presenters whose insights and contributions enrich today's dialogue. Your collective expertise significantly enhances our shared understanding and our capacity for meaningful impact.

Though we gather virtually, I firmly believe that the intellectual exchanges and professional networks cultivated during this conference will resonate beyond our screens, catalysing ongoing research initiatives, policy developments, and collaborative partnerships.

Once again, welcome, and I wish you all an insightful, productive, and inspiring conference.

Thank you.

PROF. DR. BETÜL GÜR

**Saygıdeğer Rektör Danışmanım, Sayın
Meslektaşlarım, Değerli Katılımcılar,**

Jean Monnet Chair for AB'nin Birliği Döngüsel
Ekonomi Politikaları ve Sürdürülebilirlik olarak
düzenlemekte olduğumuz "FINAL KONFERANSI"
NA HEPİNİZ HOŞ GELDİNİZ.

3 yıl süren bir emeğin, güzel bir ekip çalışmasının
sonundayız. Bu süre içinde derslerle,
workshoplar, seminerler, kış okulu ve yaz okulu
gibi akademik etkinliklerle sürdürülebilirliğin ve
döngüsellüğün önemini anlatmaya, toplumsal
farkındalık yaratmaya çalıştık. Bu konuyla ilgili
başta EU olmak üzere Türkiye'de ve dünyada
gelişmeleri ele aldık.

Kürsü üyeleri Prof. Dr. Elçin AYKAÇ ALP ve Doç.
Dr. Sabri ÖZ, Doktora Öğrencisi ve Uzman Güllü
SONAKALAN ve asistan öğrencilerimiz Rimon
AHMED, Aslıgül DEMİREL ve Sayed Abdul Kerim
HAQIQ'e teşekkür ederim.

Bugün birbirinden değerli keynote
konuşmacılarımız var: Professor Franco
MOSCONI, Professor Murat Ali YÜLEK ve
Armağan VURDU. Kendilerine bizi
onurlandırdıkları için teşekkür ediyorum.

Bütün panelistlerimize ve katılımcılarımıza
teşekkür ediyorum.

Döngüsel ekonomi ve sürdürülebilirlikle ilgili yeni
akademik çalışmalarda, yeni projelerde
işbirliğimizin devamını diliyorum,

Saygılarımla,

**Honourable Rector Counsellor Professor
ÇANKAYA, Esteemed Colleagues, and
Distinguished Participants,**

Welcome to the FINAL CONFERENCE organised
by the Jean Monnet Chair for EU's Circular
Economy Policies and Sustainability. After 3 years
of hard work and great teamwork, we have finally
reached the end. During this time, we have
attempted to raise social awareness of the
importance of sustainability and circularity by
delivering academic activities such as lectures,
workshops, seminars, winter and summer
schools. We have discussed developments
related to this topic, focusing primarily on the EU
but also considering Türkiye and the rest of the
world. I'd like to thank Chair Members Professor
Elçin AYKAÇ ALP and Associate Professor Sabri
ÖZ, Postgraduate student and Expert Güllü
SONAKALAN, our assistant students Rimon
AHMED, Aslıgül DEMİREL, and Sayed Abdul
Kerim HAQIQ.

Today, we have some Distinguished Keynote
Speakers: Professor Franco MOSCONI, Full
Professor of Industrial Economics at the
University of Parma, Professor Murat Ali YÜLEK,
Rector of OSTİM Technical University and
Professor of Industrial Policy, AND, Dr. Armağan
VURDU, Secretary General of the Istanbul
Minerals and Metals Exporters Association. I'd like
to thank them for honouring us with their
presence. I'd also like to thank all our panellists
and participants. I look forward to continuing to
collaborate with you on new academic studies and
projects related to the circularity, sustainability,
industrialisation, digital and green transformation.
Thank you so much.

Best regards,

KEYNOTE SPEECH

IPCEIs (2018-2024)

- 10 European projects
- Supranational cooperation
- Private-public partnerships
- Strategic sectors (e.g., microelectronics, batteries, hydrogen ...)

IPCEI	Participating countries	Participating projects	EU budget (2018-2024)	Co-funding (non-EU)	Participating Member States
EUROPEAN MICROELECTRONICS	29	43	3,0	0,5	DE, FR, IT, NL, PL, PT, RO, SI, SK, UK
EUROPEAN BATTERY	17	78	3,2	1	BE, DE, FR, IT, NL, PL, PT, RO, SI, SK, UK
EUROPEAN HYDROGEN	42	48	2,9	1	BE, DE, FR, IT, NL, PL, PT, RO, SI, SK, UK
EUROPEAN MICROELECTRONICS	35	41	5,4	0,5	BE, DE, FR, IT, NL, PL, PT, RO, SI, SK, UK
EUROPEAN BATTERY	28	38	6,2	1	BE, DE, FR, IT, NL, PL, PT, RO, SI, SK, UK
EUROPEAN HYDROGEN	56	68	6,1	15,7	BE, DE, FR, IT, NL, PL, PT, RO, SI, SK, UK
EUROPEAN MICROELECTRONICS	19	19	3,2	1,4	BE, DE, FR, IT, NL, PL, PT, RO, SI, SK, UK
EUROPEAN BATTERY	32	38	6,9	3,4	BE, DE, FR, IT, NL, PL, PT, RO, SI, SK, UK
EUROPEAN HYDROGEN	11	13	3,4	3,2	BE, DE, FR, IT, NL, PL, PT, RO, SI, SK, UK
IPCEI (TOTAL)	233	247	17,2	19	22 Member States, 48 non-EU countries, 1000 companies, 10000 jobs

Prof. Franco Meschini

Green and Blended Developmental Finance

Murat Yulek
Ostim Technical University

Jean Monnet Chair for EU Circular Economic Policies and Sustainability (CESPEU)
Online Keynote Speech
28 July 2025

Prof. Franco Meschini

Prof. Dr. Murat Yulek

Uğur Aksoy, PhD

PROF. FRANCO MOSCONI

At the CESPEU Final Conference, Prof. Dr. Franco Mosconi delivered a keynote address titled “The EU’s Circular Economy Policies and Sustainability.” The speech explored the evolution of the New European Industrial Policy (NIP) and its alignment with the EU’s sustainability and competitiveness objectives, offering insights relevant to the conference’s focus on circular economy principles and EU-Turkey collaboration.

Prof. Dr. Mosconi outlined the NIP’s progression through distinct phases: the integrated approach (2002–2014, Prodi and Barroso Commissions), the holistic approach (2014–2019, Juncker Commission), and the twin ecological and digital transitions (2019–2024, von der Leyen Commission). The NIP emphasizes enabling technologies, research and development, and strategic sectors such as microelectronics, batteries, and hydrogen to drive structural transformation toward sustainable industries.

Central to the address was the 2024 Draghi Report, which proposes three pillars for enhancing European competitiveness: closing the innovation gap, integrating decarbonization with competitiveness, and reducing external dependencies. Decarbonization is presented as an opportunity to lower energy costs and advance clean technologies, supported by sectoral policies like joint procurement in energy markets. Prof. Dr. Mosconi also addressed the EU’s automotive sector, highlighting its transition to electric vehicles and the industry’s advocacy for technology neutrality to balance environmental and economic goals, reflecting a reevaluation of the 2019 European Green Deal’s targets (e.g., net-zero emissions by 2050, 55% reduction in greenhouse gases by 2030).

Prof. Dr. Mosconi underscored the need for institutional reform, advocating for expanded EU-level initiatives (e.g., IPCEIs, Horizon, Erasmus+) and the development of “European Champions” inspired by Airbus. Drawing on the historical Schuman Plan (1952), which unified coal and steel under the ECSC, he proposed similar integration for contemporary strategic resources like chips, AI, and pharmaceuticals. The success of CERN was cited as a model for international collaboration in cutting-edge research.

CESPEU 2025 Final Konferansı’nda, Prof. Dr. Franco Mosconi, “The EU’s Circular Economy Policies and Sustainability” başlıklı bir açılış konuşması yaptı. Konuşma, Yeni Avrupa Sanayi Politikası’nın (NIP) evrimini ve AB’nin sürdürülebilirlik ile rekabet gücü hedefleriyle uyumunu ele aldı; döngüsel ekonomi ilkelerine ve AB-Türkiye iş birliğine odaklanan konferans temasına değerli içgörüler sundu.

Prof. Dr. Franco Mosconi, NIP’nin gelişimini şu aşamalar üzerinden özetledi: entegre yaklaşım (2002–2014, Prodi ve Barroso Komisyonları), bütüncül yaklaşım (2014–2019, Juncker Komisyonu) ve çift ekolojik ve dijital dönüşüm (2019–2024, von der Leyen Komisyonu). NIP, enabling teknolojiler, araştırma ve geliştirme ile mikroelektronik, batarya ve hidrojen gibi stratejik sektörlere odaklanarak sürdürülebilir endüstrilere doğru yapısal dönüşümü hedeflemektedir.

Konuşmanın merkezinde, Avrupa’nın rekabet gücünü artırmak için üç temel direk öneren 2024 Draghi Raporu yer aldı: yenilik açığını kapatma, karbonsuzlaşmayı rekabet gücüyle entegre etme ve dış bağımlılıkları azaltma. Karbonsuzlaşma, enerji maliyetlerini düşürme ve temiz teknolojilerde öncülük yapma fırsatı olarak sunulmakta, enerji piyasalarında ortak satın alma gibi sektörel politikalarla desteklenmektedir. Prof. Dr. Mosconi, Avrupa’nın otomotiv sektörüne de değindi; elektrikli araçlara geçişi ve sektörün çevresel ile ekonomik hedefleri dengelemek için teknoloji nötrlüğü talebini vurguladı. Bu, 2019 Avrupa Yeşil Mutabakatı’nın hedeflerinin (örneğin, 2050’de net sıfır emisyon, 2030’da 1990’a kıyasla %55 daha az sera gazı) yeniden değerlendirilmesini yansıtmaktadır.

Prof. Dr. Mosconi, bu hedefleri desteklemek için kurumsal reforma ihtiyaç olduğunu vurguladı; IPCEI’ler, Horizon ve Erasmus+ gibi AB düzeyinde girişimlerin genişletilmesini ve Airbus modelinden esinlenen “Avrupa Şampiyonları”nın geliştirilmesini önerdi. 1952’de kömür ve çeliği ECSC altında birleştiren Schuman Planı’nı, çip, yapay zeka ve ilaç gibi günümüz stratejik kaynakları için bir model olarak sundu. CERN’in ileri araştırma alanındaki uluslararası iş birliği başarısı da bir örnek olarak gösterildi.

PROF. DR. MURAT ALİ YÜLEK

At the CESPEU Final Conference, Prof. Dr. Murat Yülek delivered a keynote address titled “Green and Blended Developmental Finance.” The speech explored the critical role of financial systems in supporting sustainable development and economic growth, with a focus on the contributions of Development Finance Institutions (DFIs) in addressing gaps in incomplete financial markets, particularly in developing countries (DCs).

Prof. Dr. Murat Yülek emphasized the financial system’s role as a conduit for transforming societal savings into investments, a process that carries significant social and economic responsibility for long-term growth and sustainability. Drawing on his works, including *Industrial Policy and Sustainable Development* (Springer, 2018) and *Financing Sustainable Development in Africa* (Palgrave Macmillan, 2018), he highlighted the concept of the “Industrial Layer,” which encompasses industrial firms, managers, workers, entrepreneurs, and financial institutions. This layer requires tailored financial solutions to meet diverse needs, extending beyond traditional industrial firms to support broader economic ecosystems.

The keynote addressed the limitations of capital markets in DCs, where incomplete financial systems fail to adequately serve economic development. Prof. Dr. Yülek proposed DFIs as “second-best” solutions to bridge this gap, acting as investment bankers by providing long-term funding at reasonable rates, equity financing, and support for venture capital and peer-to-peer funding. He stressed the need for DFIs to adopt innovative tools, robust risk management, appropriate regulation, and skilled human resources to effectively channel funds to disadvantaged sectors, aligning with green and sustainable development goals.

CESPEU Final Konferansı’nda, Prof. Dr. Murat Yülek, “Green and Blended Developmental Finance” başlıklı ana konuşması yaptı. Konuşma, finansal sistemlerin sürdürülebilir kalkınma ve ekonomik büyümeyi desteklemedeki kritik rolünü ele aldı; özellikle gelişmekte olan ülkelerde (DCs) eksik finansal piyasaların boşluklarını doldurmada Kalkınma Finansmanı Kurumlarının (DFI’ler) katkılarına odaklandı.

Prof. Dr. Murat Yülek, finansal sistemin toplumsal tasarrufları yatırımlara dönüştüren bir kanal olarak uzun vadeli büyüme ve sürdürülebilirlik için önemli bir sosyal ve ekonomik sorumluluk taşıdığını vurguladı. *Industrial Policy and Sustainable Development* (Springer, 2018) ve *Financing Sustainable Development in Africa* (Palgrave Macmillan, 2018) gibi çalışmalarına dayanarak, endüstriyel firmalar, yöneticiler, işçiler, girişimciler ve finansal kuruluşları kapsayan “Endüstriyel Katman” kavramını öne çıkardı. Bu katman, geleneksel endüstriyel firmaların ötesine geçerek daha geniş ekonomik ekosistemleri desteklemek için özel finansal çözümler gerektirir.

Konuşma, DCs’de sermaye piyasalarının ekonomik kalkınmayı yeterince desteklemede başarısız olduğu eksik finansal sistemlerin sınırlılıklarını ele aldı. Prof. Dr. Yülek, DFI’leri bu boşluğu doldurmak için “ikinci en iyi” çözümler olarak önerdi; yatırım bankacısı olarak hareket ederek uygun oranlarda uzun vadeli finansman, öz sermaye finansmanı ve girişim sermayesi ile eşler arası fonlama desteği sağlama çağrısında bulundu. DFI’lerin, yeşil ve sürdürülebilir kalkınma hedefleriyle uyumlu olarak dezavantajlı sektörlere fon yönlendirmek için yenilikçi araçlar, sağlam risk yönetimi, uygun düzenleme ve yetkin insan kaynakları benimsemesi gerektiğini vurguladı.

DR. ARMAĞAN VURDU

Ladies and Gentlemen,

It is a privilege to welcome you all to today's conference. Although we are not physically together, I am very pleased that this digital platform brings us together across institutions and borders to discuss such a vital topic.

First of all, I would like to sincerely thank the faculty members of Istanbul Ticaret University, and especially Professor Betül Gür, for kindly inviting me as a keynote speaker.

It is also an honour to share this platform with our other keynote speakers: Professor Murat Yülek, Rector of OSTİM Teknik Üniversitesi, whose work on industrial policy and development has been very inspiring; and Professor Franco Mosconi, from the University of Parma, a leading expert on European industrial transformation.

Today's programme is truly rich and diverse. Our panellists will explore circular economy and sustainability from many different angles from Türkiye's new climate law to innovation, finance, gender, and cross-sector best practices.

We'll also hear sector-specific insights from the textile, agriculture, aviation, and construction industries.

This variety shows how circularity is a complex, multi-dimensional topic — and reminds us why dialogue and collaboration across sectors are so important to create real change. Let me briefly introduce the institution I represent. Istanbul Mineral and Metals Exporters' Association (IMMIB) covers six major sectors: namely steel, ferrous and non-ferrous metals, chemicals, electronics, jewelry and mining. These are energy-intensive and carbon-intensive industries, making up about 35% of Türkiye's total exports.

Because of our sectoral profile, we are closely involved with the European Union's Green Deal and the Carbon Border Adjustment Mechanism (CBAM). As Türkiye's largest export destination, the EU is reshaping market access rules around environmental performance. For our exporters, decarbonization is a matter of market access and global competitiveness. That's why IMMIB closely monitors EU policies, informs its member companies, develops projects and partnerships, and provides many training programs through IMMIB Akademi. We also work through IMMIB EU Projects

Sayın Bayanlar ve Baylar,

Bugünkü konferansa hepiniz hoş geldiniz. Fiziksel olarak bir arada olmasak da, bu dijital platformun bizi kurumlar ve sınırlar ötesinde bir araya getirerek böylesine önemli bir konuyu tartışmamızı sağladığından dolayı çok memnunuz.

Öncelikle, İstanbul Ticaret Üniversitesi öğretim üyelerine ve özellikle Profesör Betül Gür'e beni ana konuşmacı olarak davet ettikleri için içtenlikle teşekkür ederim.

Bu platformu diğer ana konuşmacılarımızla paylaşmak da benim için bir onurdur: Endüstri politikası ve kalkınma alanındaki çalışmalarını çok ilham verici olan OSTİM Teknik Üniversitesi Rektörü Profesör Murat Yülek ve Avrupa endüstri dönüşümünün önde gelen uzmanlarından Parma Üniversitesi'nden Profesör Franco Mosconi.

Bugünkü program gerçekten zengin ve çeşitlidir. Panelistlerimiz, Türkiye'nin yeni iklim yasasından inovasyon, finans, cinsiyet ve sektörler arası en iyi uygulamalara kadar birçok farklı açıdan döngüsel ekonomi ve sürdürülebilirliği ele alacaklar.

Ayrıca tekstil, tarım, havacılık ve inşaat sektörlerinden sektörlere özgü içgörüler de dinleyeceğiz.

Bu çeşitlilik, döngüsellüğün ne kadar karmaşık ve çok boyutlu bir konu olduğunu gösteriyor ve gerçek bir değişim yaratmak için sektörler arası diyalog ve işbirliğinin neden bu kadar önemli olduğunu bize hatırlatıyor. Temsil ettiğim kurumu kısaca tanıyayım. İstanbul Maden ve Metal İhracatçıları Birliği (IMMIB), çelik, demir ve demir dışı metaller, kimyasallar, elektronik, mücevher ve madencilik olmak üzere altı ana sektörü kapsamaktadır. Bunlar, Türkiye'nin toplam ihracatının yaklaşık %35'ini oluşturan enerji ve karbon yoğun sektörlerdir.

Sektörel profilimiz nedeniyle, Avrupa Birliği'nin Yeşil Anlaşması ve Karbon Sınır Ayarlama Mekanizması (CBAM) ile yakından ilgileniyoruz. Türkiye'nin en büyük ihracat pazarı olan AB, çevresel performans etrafında pazar erişim kurallarını yeniden şekillendiriyor. İhracatçılarımız için karbonsuzlaşma, pazar erişimi ve küresel rekabet gücü meselesidir. Bu nedenle IMMIB, AB politikalarını yakından takip ediyor, üye şirketlerini bilgilendiriyor, projeler ve ortaklıklar geliştiriyor ve IMMIB Akademi aracılığıyla birçok eğitim programı sunuyor. Ayrıca IMMIB AB Projeleri Departmanı aracılığıyla sürdürülebilirlik odaklı hibe projelerini tasarlamak ve uygulamak için

Department to design and implement sustainability-focused grant projects. At the outset of my speech about today's agenda, I would like to point out a striking fact. Last week, on July 24th, humanity reached Earth Overshoot Day 2025. According to the Global Footprint Network, Earth Overshoot Day marks the moment when humanity exhausted nature's annual budget, meaning we have already used up all the ecological resources the planet can regenerate in a year.

We are depleting local resources and increasing carbon dioxide in the atmosphere to cover this gap. Currently, we're using nature 80% faster than the Earth can replace it, as if we had almost two planets. We use too much because we take, make, and waste without thinking about renewal. This wastes natural resources and causes problems like deforestation, soil degradation, loss of wildlife, increased carbon dioxide in the atmosphere, more extreme weather events, and threats to our food supply.

So today, when we talk about circular economy and sustainability, it's not just about protecting the environment. It's about physical and economic survival, trade resilience, and industrial transformation. Reducing carbon emissions is not only an ecological responsibility but also a strategic necessity for preserving our economic competitiveness.

For this reason, the circular economy approach is vital both for resource efficiency and decarbonization goals. The circular economy means using materials and energy for as long as we can. It focuses on making products last longer, reducing waste, and designing items for reuse. This contrasts sharply with the linear 'take-make-dispose' model that still dominates today's economy. Global natural resource use has more than tripled over the past 50 years and it's still growing by over 2.3% every year. With the way we produce and consume now, and the problems caused by climate change, it's unlikely we can meet the needs of over 8 billion people in the coming years.

As a result, global initiatives such as the United Nations Sustainable Development Goals and the European Green Deal focus on transforming production models and changing consumption habits worldwide.

With a linear approach each year, we throw away about \$2.6 trillion worth of fast-moving consumer goods. That's nearly 80% of the material value of these products gone to waste. However, with a circular approach, we could extend their lifecycle, reintegrate materials into new production processes, and preserve

çalışıyoruz. Bugünkü gündemle ilgili konuşmamın başında dikkat çekici bir gerçeğe değinmek istiyorum. Geçen hafta, 24 Temmuz'da, insanlık 2025 Dünya Aşım Günü'ne ulaştı. Global Footprint Network'e göre, Dünya Aşım Günü, insanlığın doğanın yıllık bütçesini tükettiği anı işaret ediyor, yani gezegenin bir yılda yenileyebileceği tüm ekolojik kaynakları çoktan tükettik.

Bu açığı kapatmak için yerel kaynakları tüketiyor ve atmosferdeki karbondioksit miktarını artırıyoruz. Şu anda, sanki iki gezegenimiz varmış gibi, doğayı Dünya'nın yenileyebileceğinden %80 daha hızlı tüketiyoruz. Yenilenmeyi düşünmeden alıyoruz, üretiyoruz ve israf ediyoruz, bu yüzden çok fazla tüketiyoruz. Bu, doğal kaynakları israf ediyor ve ormansızlaşma, toprak bozulması, yaban hayatının kaybı, atmosferdeki karbondioksit artışına, daha aşırı hava olaylarına ve gıda tedarikimize yönelik tehditlere neden oluyor.

Günümüzde döngüsel ekonomi ve sürdürülebilirlikten bahsettiğimizde, bu sadece çevreyi korumakla ilgili değildir. Fiziksel ve ekonomik hayatta kalma, ticaretin dayanıklılığı ve endüstriyel dönüşümle ilgilidir. Karbon emisyonlarını azaltmak sadece ekolojik bir sorumluluk değil, aynı zamanda ekonomik rekabet gücümüzü korumak için stratejik bir gerekliliktir.

Bu nedenle, döngüsel ekonomi yaklaşımı hem kaynak verimliliği hem de karbonsuzlaşma hedefleri için hayati önem taşımaktadır. Döngüsel ekonomi, malzemeleri ve enerjiyi mümkün olduğunca uzun süre kullanmak anlamına gelir. Ürünlerin daha uzun ömürlü olmasını sağlamak, atıkları azaltmak ve yeniden kullanım için ürünler tasarlamak üzerine odaklanır. Bu, günümüz ekonomisinde hala hakim olan doğrusal "al-yap-at" modeliyle keskin bir tezat oluşturur. Küresel doğal kaynak kullanımı son 50 yılda üç katından fazla arttı ve hala her yıl %2,3'ün üzerinde büyümeye devam ediyor. Şu anda üretim ve tüketim şeklimiz ve iklim değişikliğinin neden olduğu sorunlar göz önüne alındığında, önümüzdeki yıllarda 8 milyardan fazla insanın ihtiyaçlarını karşılayabilmemiz olası görünmemektedir.

Sonuç olarak, Birleşmiş Milletler Sürdürülebilir Kalkınma Hedefleri ve Avrupa Yeşil Anlaşması gibi küresel girişimler, üretim modellerini dönüştürmeye ve dünya çapında tüketim alışkanlıklarını değiştirmeye odaklanmaktadır.

Her yıl doğrusal bir yaklaşımla, yaklaşık 2,6 trilyon dolar değerinde hızlı tüketim mallarını çöpe atıyoruz.

much of that lost value. According to the 2025 Circularity Gap Report, the vast majority of materials entering the global economy are still virgin materials. The share of secondary materials has declined from 7.2% in 2018 to just 6.9% in 2021. It highlights the critical importance of systemic change. Europe ranks among the highest in the world in terms of consumption and waste generation. Each European consumes about 14 tonnes of materials and produces 5 tonnes of waste per year. Excluding large-scale mineral waste, Europe landfills about 306 kg of waste per person and recycles nearly half of the waste it generates. While still insufficient, waste management in Europe continues to improve. The EU has adopted a Circular Economy Action Plan, pledging billions of euros to reach net-zero emissions by 2032. But challenges remain especially in financing. The European Investment Bank invested €3.8 billion in circular projects from 2019 to 2023, which is just a fraction of the €55 billion needed annually. Circularity also presents a major economic opportunity. In Europe alone, it could unlock over €1 trillion in value by 2050. It's also a strong driver of employment, with the potential to create up to 8 million jobs by 2030. And let's not forget the service side; repair, maintenance, battery replacement, and refurbishment could grow into a €70 billion market by the end of this decade. What's more, consumer expectations are shifting. A 2024 survey conducted in six countries including Germany, the UK, and the US, showed that 64% of consumers rank sustainability among their top three purchasing criteria. Sustainability is no longer a "nice-to-have." It is becoming a core business requirement. In conclusion I would like to mention once again circularity is not just a choice, but an essential requirement for both ecological balance and lasting economic prosperity. Our current consumption habits demand more than one Earth can provide, yet we have only one. Embracing a circular economy is the only viable path to securing sustainability and long-term growth for future generations. I sincerely hope that today's panels will inspire new ideas, foster partnerships, and accelerate the integration of circularity into production, trade, and innovation. Thank you once again to all our speakers for your contributions and to our audience for your attention.

I wish you all a productive and inspiring day.

Bu, bu ürünlerin maddi değerinin neredeyse %80'inin israf edildiği anlamına geliyor. Ancak döngüsel bir yaklaşımla, bu ürünlerin yaşam döngüsünü uzatabilir, malzemeleri yeni üretim süreçlerine yeniden entegre edebilir ve kaybedilen değer büyük bir kısmını koruyabiliriz. 2025 Döngüsellik Açığı Raporu'na göre, küresel ekonomiye giren malzemelerin büyük çoğunluğu hala işlenmemiş malzemelerdir. İkincil malzemelerin payı 2018'de %7,2 iken 2021'de sadece %6,9'a gerilemiştir. Bu durum, sistemik değişimin kritik önemini vurgulamaktadır. Avrupa, tüketim ve atık üretimi açısından dünyada en üst sıralarda yer almaktadır. Her Avrupalı yılda yaklaşık 14 ton malzeme tüketir ve 5 ton atık üretir. Büyük ölçekli maden atıkları hariç, Avrupa kişi başına yaklaşık 306 kg atık depolamakta ve ürettiği atığın neredeyse yarısını geri dönüştürmektedir. Hala yetersiz olmakla birlikte, Avrupa'da atık yönetimi iyileşmeye devam etmektedir. AB, 2032 yılına kadar net sıfır emisyonu ulaştırmak için milyarlarca avro taahhüt eden bir Döngüsel Ekonomi Eylem Planı kabul etmiştir. Ancak özellikle finansman konusunda zorluklar devam ediyor. Avrupa Yatırım Bankası, 2019'dan 2023'e kadar döngüsel projelere 3,8 milyar avro yatırım yaptı, ancak bu, yıllık olarak ihtiyaç duyulan 55 milyar avronun sadece bir kısmı. Döngüsellik aynı zamanda önemli bir ekonomik fırsat da sunuyor. Sadece Avrupa'da, 2050 yılına kadar 1 trilyon avrodan fazla değer yaratabilir. Ayrıca, 2030 yılına kadar 8 milyon iş yaratma potansiyeli ile istihdamın da güçlü bir itici gücü. Hizmet tarafını da unutmayalım; onarım, bakım, pil değişimi ve yenileme, bu on yılın sonunda 70 milyar avroluk bir pazara dönüşebilir. Dahası, tüketici beklentileri de değişiyor. Almanya, İngiltere ve ABD dahil altı ülkede 2024 yılında yapılan bir ankette, tüketicilerin %64'ünün sürdürülebilirliği en önemli üç satın alma kriteri arasında sıraladığı ortaya çıktı. Sürdürülebilirlik artık "olsa iyi olur" bir şey değil. İşletmelerin temel bir gerekliliği haline geliyor. Sonuç olarak, döngüsellik sadece bir tercih değil, ekolojik denge ve kalıcı ekonomik refah için vazgeçilmez bir gereklilik olduğunu bir kez daha belirtmek isterim. Mevcut tüketim alışkanlıklarımız, Dünya'nın sağlayabileceğinden fazlasını talep ediyor, ancak bizim sadece bir tane Dünya'mız var. Döngüsel ekonomiyi benimsemek, gelecek nesiller için sürdürülebilirliği ve uzun vadeli büyümeyi sağlamanın tek geçerli yoludur. Katkıları için tüm konuşmacılarımıza ve ilgileri için dinleyicilerimize bir kez daha teşekkür ederim.

Hepinize verimli ve ilham verici bir gün dilerim.

SESSION 1 PRESENTATIONS – Moderated by İlker KÖSE, PhD

Necla İLTER KÜÇÜKÇOLAK, Assoc. Prof., Turkish Merchantile Exchange

ORCID: 0000-0002-7097-5423

Designing Climate-Smart Sustainable Agricultural Markets: Legal Alignment of Türkiye's Climate Law with the EU and a Carbon Market Instrument Proposal for Agricultural Commodities

ABSTRACT

The Turkish Climate Law No. 7552, enacted on July 9, 2025, marks a significant milestone in the country's legal and institutional response to climate change. This paper presents a comparative legal analysis of the Turkish Climate Law and the European Climate Law (Regulation (EU) 2021/1119), examining their points of convergence and divergence in key areas such as net-zero targets, emissions trading systems (ETS), carbon sinks, and the integration of the agricultural sector into climate strategies. Special emphasis is placed on how both frameworks incorporate agriculture through carbon sink preservation, sustainable land use, and climate-resilient production systems. While EU legislation operationalizes these goals through the LULUCF (Land Use, Land-Use Change and Forestry) Regulation and the Common Agricultural Policy (CAP), Türkiye's law mandates similar protections for forests, pastures, and wetlands as key carbon sinks.

The study concludes with actionable policy recommendations aimed at enhancing Türkiye's alignment with the EU Green Deal. In particular, it explores the potential role of licensed warehouse receipts and related institutions in developing climate-linked agricultural market mechanisms and sustainable value chains. A novel policy instrument is proposed: the Carbon-Certified Agricultural Commodity (CCAC). The CCAC is designed to integrate Türkiye's licensed agricultural warehousing infrastructure into voluntary carbon markets. Under a structured Monitoring, Reporting, and Verification (MRV) framework, farmers who adopt emissions-reducing practices (e.g. minimum tillage, certified seed, organic fertilization and dripping irrigation) would be eligible to receive certified carbon credits alongside their licensed warehouse receipts. These carbon credits from Green Electronic Warehouse Receipts (Green EWRs) can be bundled with carbon offsets, enabling institutional buyers to align procurement with climate goals. Moreover, Green EWRs may benefit

from enhanced financial incentives such as preferential interest rates or increased credit limits, thereby strengthening the link between sustainable agricultural practices and rural finance.

Keywords: *Carbon-Certified Agricultural Commodity (CCAC); Green Electronic Warehouse Receipts (Green EWRs); Climate-Smart Agriculture; Climate Law*

DESIGNING CLIMATE-SMART SUSTAINABLE AGRICULTURAL PRODUCTION

- Legal Alignment of Türkiye's Climate Law with the EU Framework and a Carbon Instrument for Agricultural Commodities

Assoc. Prof. Necla İLTER KÜÇÜKÇOLAK
EVP, Turkish Mercantile Exchange

İstanbul Ticaret University
Jean Monnet Chair for EU Circular Economy Policies and Sustainability (CESPEU)
28 July 2025

The Relationship and Impact of Circular Economy and Sustainability Concepts with the Aviation Industry

Asst.Prof.Dr. Bura Sabiha Kelek
İstanbul Medipol University

Bura Sabiha KELEK, Assist. Prof., İstanbul Medipol University

ORCID: 0000-0002-9630-0280

The Relationship and Impact of Circular Economy and Sustainability Concepts with the Aviation Industry

ABSTRACT

Air transport, which is increasing rapidly, has become an important industry in terms of environmental impacts. Problems such as carbon emissions, resource consumption and waste generation make it imperative to align the aviation sector with sustainable development goals. At this point, the circular economy approach plays a key role in reducing environmental impacts by efficient use of resources and minimizing waste. Although the aviation industry is one of the fastest and most effective ways of modern transportation, it also draws attention with its negative effects on the environment. Increased flight traffic, fossil fuel use and waste generation; It constitutes a significant part of global carbon emissions. According to 2023 data, the aviation industry produces approximately 2.5% of carbon emissions worldwide. In this context, circular economy and sustainability approaches are of great importance to reduce the environmental impact of the aviation industry and increase economic efficiency. In this study, the relationship between these two concepts and the aviation industry is discussed comprehensively, current practices and challenges are analyzed, and suggestions for the future are presented.

Keywords: Aviation, Logistics, Sustainability, Circular Economy

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कल्याण मंत्रालय
MINISTRY OF
AGRICULTURE AND
FARMERS WELFARE

Yusuf GÜNGÖR, PhD (c), İstanbul Ticaret University

ORCID: 0000-0001-6480-0929

Ayben KOY, Assoc. Prof., İstanbul Ticaret University

ORCID: 0000-0002-2506-6634

Gender on Board: How Female Representation Strengthens Governance and Profitability

ABSTRACT

This study investigates the impact of corporate governance practices on the financial performance of firms listed in the Borsa Istanbul Corporate Governance Index (BIST XKURY) from 2010 to 2022, using panel data analysis. The four subcomponents of corporate governance rating—shareholders, public disclosure and transparency, stakeholders, and board of directors—served as independent variables, while return on assets (ROA), return on equity (ROE), and earnings per share (EPS) are used as performance indicators. Firm size and leverage are included as control variables. To examine the role of gender diversity, the sample is divided into firms with less than 25% and at least 25% female board representation. This approach aimed to reveal the potential impact of gender diversity on financial performance. The findings indicate that the effects of corporate governance practices on financial performance differ according to the subcomponents and the proportion of female board members. In particular, firms with higher female board representation exhibit a stronger positive relationship between board effectiveness and profitability, highlighting the strategic value of gender diversity in enhancing governance quality and financial outcomes. These findings underscore the dual importance—both ethical and economic—of promoting female participation in corporate leadership.

Keywords: Corporate Governance, Financial Performance, Gender Diversity

Şüheda BARAN SATILMIŞ, PhD. İstanbul Ticaret University

ORCID: 0000-0001-5176-7971

Mapping The Evolution of Circular Economy and Sustainability Research

ABSTRACT

In recent years, the acceleration of environmental degradation, the risk of depletion of natural resources and the deepening effects of climate change have necessitated the development of new economic approaches in line with the principles of sustainable development. In this context, the circular economy stands out as a holistic approach that aims to increase resource efficiency, reduce waste production and harmonize economic growth with environmental sustainability. Today, the concepts of circular economy and sustainability are at the center of environmental and economic transformation policies and are addressed in many academic studies. However, bibliometric analyses in the literature generally examine these two concepts separately or are limited to a specific sectoral context. It is observed that the concept of sustainability is often given secondary importance in studies on the development process of the circular economy literature, and similarly, the concept of circular economy is not evaluated comprehensively in sustainability-focused bibliometric analyses. Therefore, the study presents a bibliometric analysis focusing on publications published in Scopus and Web of Science (WoS) databases between 2008 and 2025 and containing the concepts of “circular economy” and “sustainability” in their titles, abstracts or keywords. In the analysis performed via VOSviewer software, conceptual clusters were visualized through the development trends of the relevant literature, publication density, the most influential authors, countries and institutions, and keyword matches. The findings reveal that the circular economy literature is gradually evolving into an interdisciplinary structure and is strongly integrated with sustainable development goals. In this context, this study aims to contribute to filling this gap in the literature by revealing the academic interaction and development trends between these concepts.

Keywords: Circular economy, Sustainability, Bibliometric analysis

Tolga ERKAN, Assoc. Prof., OSTİM Technical University Faculty

ORCID: 0000-0002-7578-2065

Bahattin Gökhan TOPAL, Coordinator, Technology Transfer Office, OSTİM Technical University Faculty

ORCID: 0000-0002-0022-1976

Green Cities and Urban Biodiversity

ABSTRACT

This review article explores the pivotal role of urban biodiversity in addressing the accelerating ecological degradation affecting global ecosystems. It argues that biodiversity must be repositioned not only as a conservation goal but also as a functional element of urban resilience, capable of mitigating pressing environmental challenges such as soil depletion, deforestation, watershed collapse, and disrupted biogeochemical cycles. The study emphasizes the urgency of integrating nature into urban and territorial development to enhance ecological integrity, public health, social cohesion, and economic sustainability. The article's scope includes diverse strategies—rewilding, ecological restoration, and green infrastructure planning—highlighting their capacity to deliver essential ecosystem services such as air purification, water regulation, and climate adaptation. It advocates for nature-based solutions that are both economically viable and socially inclusive, especially in rapidly urbanizing regions where their impact is most critical. As urban expansion intensifies, biodiversity must be embedded across all scales of urban planning—from city-wide green corridors to neighborhood initiatives—ensuring coexistence between humans and other species despite altered environmental conditions. Urban biodiversity also strengthens human-nature connections, enhances quality of life, and promotes cost-effective alternatives to engineered systems. Moreover, it contributes to job creation, cultural vitality, and participatory governance. Ultimately, the transition toward green cities offers profound ecological, health-related, socio-economic, and educational benefits. By integrating biodiversity into the urban fabric, cities can evolve into more sustainable, equitable, and resilient habitats capable of responding to current and future socio-environmental challenges.

Keywords: Ecological resilience, Green infrastructure, Nature-based solutions, Sustainable urban development, Urban biodiversity.

SESSION 2 PRESENTATIONS – Moderated by Elçin AYKAÇ ALP, Prof. Dr.

THE TWO TYPES OF CARBON

The Problem: A Building's Total Carbon Footprint

To solve the problem, it is important to understand its two parts.

- Operational Carbon: The energy used every day for lighting, heating, and cooling
- Embodied Carbon: Emissions from materials, manufacturing, and construction
- Embodied carbon may account for up to 50% of lifecycle emissions by 2050 (Pomponi & Moncaster, 2016)

M. Towsif Hasan

M. Towsif HASAN, Professor, Melbourne University, Australia

ORCID: 0009-0004-8357-6634

Closing the Loop: A Digital Twin Framework for Whole-Life Carbon Optimization

ABSTRACT

This paper explores the potential of a unified digital framework to create a continuous sustainability feedback loop in the built environment. The primary objective is to investigate how integrating two critical phases — calculating embodied carbon during design and monitoring operational carbon post-construction — can form a dynamic, self-improving system for decarbonization.

Focusing on the entire building lifecycle, this research aims to address the significance of embodied carbon, which can constitute up to 50% of a new building's footprint by 2050 (Pomponi & Moncaster, 2016). While operational carbon has long dominated policy and performance metrics, the irreversible nature of embodied emissions requires robust early-stage decision-making tools. The feedback loop spans from initial material specification to real-time monitoring and iterative performance calibration.

A multi-stage, mixed-methods approach will be employed. First, a systematic literature review identifies gaps in Whole-Life Carbon Assessment (WLCA) practices. Next, semi-structured interviews with stakeholders (designers, engineers, facility managers, among others) gather insights and practical workflow challenges. Finally, a comparative case study can help simulate how post-occupancy operational data — integrated via a Digital Twin — can refine embodied carbon estimates for future design iterations.

The framework has the potential to contribute to significant embodied emission reductions during design and continuously optimize operational carbon, thus narrowing the performance gap. The system has the potential to function as a dynamic "material passport," enhancing end-of-life material recovery and reuse. This continuous data loop reinforces circular economy principles by supporting adaptive reuse, predictive maintenance, and verifiable low-carbon performance across the building lifecycle.

Keywords: *Embodied Carbon, Operational Carbon, Digital Twin, Whole-Life Carbon Assessment, Sustainable Construction, Circular Economy.*

WHAT IS A DIGITAL TWIN?

A living, digital replica of the physical building.

- Continuously updated with real-time sensor data
- Tracks energy use, occupancy, air quality, performance
- Enables comparisons between predicted and actual outcomes

01 Links Building Information Modeling (BIM) from the design stage with Building Management Systems (BMS) used during operation.

02 Enables Whole-Life Carbon Assessment (WLCA) by integrating embodied and operational carbon data across the building's lifecycle

03 Sensor inputs such as temperature, energy demand, and occupancy allow for continuous performance monitoring and adjustment

04 This system is aimed to support machine learning algorithms to refine future design decisions based on actual building performance

M. Towsif Hasan

M. Towsif Hasan

Ayben KOY, Professor, İstanbul Ticaret University

ORCID: 0000-0002-2506-6634

Semra DEMİR, Assist. Prof., Burdur Mehmet Akif Ersoy University

ORCID: 0000-0003-4597-7061

Modeling the Dynamics of Sustainable Finance: A Nonlinear Approach to Borsa Istanbul Sustainability Indices

ABSTRACT

This study investigates the liquidity and returns of the Borsa Istanbul Sustainability Indices using nonlinear econometric methods over the period from January 2, 2015, to May 30, 2025. By employing advanced nonlinear time series techniques, such as threshold models, the research aims to capture complex dynamics and asymmetric behaviors that linear models may fail to detect. The findings contribute to a deeper understanding of the efficiency and risk-return profile of sustainable investments in emerging markets. The results confirm the nonlinear behavior between the returns, and return and liquidity with different dynamics in high vs. low regimes. For return, both MTAR-ECM models confirm the presence of error correction mechanisms, meaning a long-run equilibrium exists between the variables. Short-run effects vary across models, but are significant. Predictive performance is weak in the SETAR model (high MAPE), though ECM models perform better. Liquidity dynamics between the sustainability and corporate governance indices are nonlinear and regime-dependent. The SETAR model confirms the presence of different behaviors in high vs. low liquidity regimes. The MTAR-ECM model supports the existence of a long-run equilibrium and significant short-run spillovers. Liquidity shocks are asymmetrically transmitted, with DY (likely the governance index) exerting a stronger downward pressure. The results provide valuable insights for policymakers, institutional investors, and researchers interested in the evolving role of ESG (Environmental, Social, and Governance) factors in financial markets.

Keywords: Sustainability, nonlinearity, Borsa Istanbul.

Recep Ali KÜÇÜKÇOLAK, Assoc. Prof., İstanbul Ticaret University

ORCID: 0000-0001-7959-1242

Effects of the New Climate Law on Financial Markets in Türkiye

ABSTRACT

The Climate Law enacted in Türkiye contains quite comprehensive innovations. The new law, which was prepared for net zero emission and green development targets, will lead to significant impacts and results such as new markets and new financial product issuances in financial markets such as emission trading system, voluntary carbon markets, primary markets, offsetting practices, market-based mechanisms for carbon pricing, Carbon Market Board, carbon regulation mechanism at the border. In this study, the effects of the new Climate Law on Turkey's financial markets both during the transition phase for the preparation of action plans and during the subsequent implementation phases are analyzed in comparison with the practices of other countries, especially the European Union. The results of the study are expected to contribute to practitioners and policy makers on sustainable development and transition to a green economy.

Keywords: Climate Law, Financial Markets, Carbon Markets, Emissions Trading System, Sustainability, Green Economy

Abdul Baghi NABIYEV, İstanbul School of Technology, Azerbaijan

Sustainable and Climate Finance within the Framework of the Circular Economy: Challenges and Opportunities for Central Banks

ABSTRACT

Climate change and environmental degradation present systemic risks to macro-financial stability and the long-term resilience of the global financial system. As stewards of economic and price stability, central banks are increasingly acknowledging the need to incorporate climate-related and environmental risks into their supervisory, monetary, and macroprudential frameworks. This seminar offers an academically rigorous yet policy-relevant examination of the evolving landscapes of sustainable finance and climate finance, highlighting their interconnection with principles of the circular economy.

The first section of the study delves into the theoretical and regulatory foundations of sustainable finance, including the incorporation of environmental, social, and governance (ESG) factors, the taxonomy frameworks that define sustainable activities, and the financial instruments designed to direct capital toward sustainability-aligned sectors. Consideration will also be given to how sustainable finance mechanisms can facilitate circular business models, thereby enhancing resource efficiency, minimizing waste, and fostering economic regeneration. The second section focuses on the principles and instruments of climate finance, covering climate-related financial risk classification, climate disclosure frameworks (such as the TCFD, ISSB, and PCAF), and methodologies for portfolio alignment. Special emphasis is placed on the distinctive role of central banks in bolstering resilience through climate scenario analysis, stress testing, and supervisory expectations. In conclusion, this study highlights several critical challenges that financial regulators face, including the complexity of taxonomy comparability, the need for granular data, and the pervasive issue of greenwashing. Furthermore, it explores promising pathways for advancing sustainable and climate finance in the future.

Keywords: *Climate Finance, Sustainability, Circular Economy, TCFD, ISSB, PCAF, Central Bank*

SESSION 3 PRESENTATIONS – Moderated by Sabri ÖZ, Assoc. Prof. Dr.

Gizem ATEŞ, Ph.D., Research Assist., İnönü University

ORCID: 0000-0002-2678-5999

Beyhan MARŞAP, Prof., Ankara Hacı Bayram Veli University

ORCID: 0000-0003-2139-7169

Devrim HULTEN, Assoc. Prof., Lund University, Sweden

ORCID: 0000-0001-5050-175X

Circular Economy Policies and Sustainable Innovation in the Construction Sector: Sweden and Türkiye Scoping Study

ABSTRACT

Kaynak koruma, atık azaltma ve malzeme dönüşümü ilkeleri çerçevesinde geliştirilen sürdürülebilir inovasyon uygulamaları, karbon yoğun ve geleneksel yapılı inşaat sektörünün “al-yap-at” modelinden dögüsel modele geçişi için kritik öneme sahiptir. Bu çalışmanın kapsamı, farklı ulusal bağlamlarda dögüsel ekonomi politikalarının rolü ile inşaat sektöründeki sürdürülebilir inovasyon uygulamalarına odaklanmaktadır. Araştırma sorusu, İsveç ve Türkiye inşaat sektörlerinde dögüsel ekonomi politikalarının nasıl farklılaştığını keşfetmeyi amaçlamaktadır. Most Different System Design (MDSD) yaklaşımı, temel değişkenler açısından önemli farklılıklar gösteren iki ülkenin karşılaştırılmasını olanaklı kılmakta ve literatüre metodolojik katkı sunmaktadır. Çalışmanın amacı, inşaat sektöründe sürdürülebilir inovasyona yönelik ulusal yaklaşımları karşılaştırmalı olarak analiz etmektir. Bu kapsamda kapsam belirleme çalışması adımları takip edilerek, Scopus veritabanında gerçekleştirilen benchmark analizi, yapılandırılmış bir karşılaştırma çerçevesi sunmakta; veri kaynağı, amaç ve değerlendirme yöntemine göre bölümlere ayrılarak R Studio üzerinden grafiksel temsillerle desteklenmiştir. İsveç ve Türkiye'nin ulusal yaklaşımları analiz edilerek temel eğilimler, boşluklar ve güçlü alanlar belirlenmiştir. Analiz sonuçları, İsveç'in güçlü kamu politikalarıyla desteklenen dögüsel ekonomi ilkelerini inşaat sektöründeki sürdürülebilir inovasyon uygulamalarına entegre etme konusunda daha proaktif olduğunu, Türkiye'nin ise gelişme potansiyeli

taşıyan, ancak henüz erken aşamada olan bir çerçeveye sahip bulunduğunu göstermektedir. Bu çalışma, ulusal politikaların ve sektörel stratejilerin sürdürülebilir inşaat inovasyonuna entegrasyonda nasıl belirleyici rol oynadığını karşılaştırmalı bir çerçevede ortaya koymaktadır.

Keywords: İnşaat sektörü, Sürdürülebilir inovasyon, Döngüsel ekonomi.

The Final Conference of the Jean Monnet Chair for EU's Circular Economy Policies and Sustainability (CESPEU), İstanbul

«Circular Economy Policies and Sustainable Innovation in the Construction Sector: Sweden and Türkiye Scoping Study
İnşaat Sektöründe Döngüsel Ekonomi Politikaları ve Sürdürülebilir İnovasyon: İsveç ve Türkiye Kapsam Belirleme Çalışması»

Gizem ATEŞ, Ph.D., Research Assist., İnönü University
Beyhan MARŞAP, Professor, Ankara Hacı Bayram Veli University
Devrim HULTEN, Assoc. Professor, Lund University, Sweden

ECONOMIC STRUCTURE

Country	Agriculture (Value added as % GDP)	Tourism (% GDP)
Albania	16.20%	21.00%
Turkey	6.20%	11.30%
Montenegro	5.50%	27.00%
Greece	3.80%	28.30%
Croatia	3.40%	25.20%
Spain	2.40%	14.30%
Portugal	2.10%	16.70%
Italy	1.90%	13.20%
France	1.70%	9.40%
Slovenia	1.50%	10.10%

Country	Agriculture (Value added as % GDP)	Tourism (% GDP)
Nepal	27.00%	9.50%
Rwanda	25.80%	12.80%
Tanzania	24.50%	17.30%
Cambodia	22.70%	18.90%
Kenya	22.40%	15.20%
Vanuatu	21.30%	20.10%
Albania	18.00%	21.00%
Tonga	17.50%	15.20%
Guatemala	11.20%	13.50%
Fiji	8.40%	35.4%

Azmi STRINGA, PhD (c), University of Tirana, Albania

Manjola NACO, Assist., Prof., Metropolitan University Tirana, Albania

Alban KORBI, Assist. Prof., University of Tirana, Albania

From Growth to Sustainability: Rethinking Albania's Economy for Inclusive and Sustainable Development

ABSTRACT

This paper investigates whether Albania's economy, and especially the tourism and agriculture sectors, can support an inclusive and circular economic model that improves citizens' well-being and promotes long-term sustainability.

Focusing on the decade from 2013 to 2023, the study examines Albania's structural transformation in the context of rapid tourism expansion, a construction boom, and persistent underperformance in agriculture, which still employs nearly 40% of the workforce. It compares Albania's model with the EU and other tourism-intensive economies such as Croatia and Greece to evaluate if just tourism is sufficient and the role of agriculture sector in economic development. Using a mixed-methods approach, the paper analyzes macroeconomic indicators (GDP, wages, pensions, household consumption, sectoral value added, demographics), cost-of-living and price data. The analysis draws from international databases, government sources, and sectoral studies, framed within sustainable economy and inclusive development theory. Findings show that while Albania's GDP has increased, wages, pensions, household consumption, and agricultural productivity have lagged behind. Households face rising costs, particularly in food and non-alcoholic beverages, partly due to tourism-driven inflation and internal market inefficiencies, yet receive limited direct benefits from economic growth and currency appreciation.

Agriculture remains disconnected from the tourism value chain, missing opportunities for local income generation, while local currency appreciation hurts producers.

The paper argues that without circular linkages and a closed and efficient connection of local producers and consumers, Albanian households and producers risk absorbing the costs of growth without sharing in its benefits. A shift toward circular and integrated policy approaches is essential

Alara SAYGI, Researcher, European Relations Club

ORCID: 0009-0007-2418-7884

Sergen GAYRETLİ, Researcher, European Relations Club

ORCID: 0009-0003-2453-5974

Pathways to Modernisation CBAM's Role in Transforming the Türkiye-EU Customs Union

ABSTRACT

The Customs Union between Türkiye and the EU, established in the name of deeper economic integration and facilitation of seamless trade, currently stands at a critical juncture due to the EU's recently introduced Carbon Border Adjustment Mechanism (CBAM). Being a key component of the EU's broader climate strategy, CBAM is projected to prevent carbon leakage by imposing carbon tariffs on imports from countries that have not adopted domestic emissions pricing systems matching EU standards. Rather, it creates potential trade frictions within the established Customs Union with Türkiye. As Türkiye continues to resist implementing its own carbon pricing mechanism, high-emission sectors such as steel, cement, and textiles, the substantial economic and regulatory challenges stand to persist under the Customs Union.

This paper analyses how the implications of Türkiye's reluctance to establish domestic carbon pricing on the sustainability and functionality of the Türkiye-EU Customs Union. It then explores the emerging incompatibility between Türkiye's economic policy and the EU's climate ambitions under the lenses of how CBAM could undermine decades of carefully structured economic interdependence and by critically assessing these dynamics the paper comes to propose that the modernisation of the Customs Union framework is essential for reconciling trade liberalisation with ambitious climate goals. This paper's methodology is a qualitative analysis combining legal and institutional review, policy evaluation, and economic impact assessment.

Keywords: European Union, Carbon Border Adjustment Mechanism, modernisation, Customs Union

Akif Emrah BÜYÜKSOMER, PhD C.

ORCID: 0009-0008-3256-8078

Federated Learning in the Circular Economy: A Systematic Literature Review

ABSTRACT

The transition towards a circular economy presents a significant paradox: while it demands intensive, cross-organizational data exchange for tracking material flows, competitive concerns and data privacy regulations severely hinder this collaborative transparency. This study's primary objective is to investigate how Federated Learning (FL), a privacy-preserving machine learning paradigm, is being positioned within academic discourse as a potential technological key to unlock this deadlock. Accordingly, this review scopes the intersection of these domains, examining scholarly literature on FL's utility in contexts essential for circularity, such as multi-stakeholder product lifecycle management and the creation of verifiable Digital Product Passports. Adopting a systematic literature review methodology, the research commenced with a structured keyword search across major academic databases, followed by a meticulous filtering process. The final collection of relevant articles was subjected to a thematic synthesis to identify core research patterns and gaps. Our analysis reveals that scholarly engagement with this field is in its infancy. A primary finding is that current research concentrates on intra-organizational FL applications, leaving a substantial gap in studies on the inter-organizational collaboration vital for a functional circular ecosystem. The review also consolidates key challenges, such as algorithmic robustness and the need for equitable incentive models, ultimately positing that FL represents a potent, yet underdeveloped, pathway for activating next-generation circular business models.

Keywords: Federated Learning, Circular Economy, Data Privacy, Digital Product Passport

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MINISTRY OF
AGRICULTURE AND
FARMERS WELFARE

Müge ÖZ, Int. Industrialists' and Businesswomen's Association (USIKAD) Chair Holder

ORCID: 0009-0004-9636-1739

Bekir Berat Yalın EKER, Adv., İstanbul School of Technology

ORCID: 0000-0003-1695-3327

Sabri ÖZ, Assoc. Prof., BeTa Science Association, İstanbul School of Technology

ORCID: 0000-0002-6280-726X

Public Relations Evaluation of the Climate Law in Turkey: A Qualitative Analysis, to be Aside or Not!

ABSTRACT

The climate law is considered a significant step that countries party to the Paris Climate Agreement are required to take, in accordance with the "fit for 55" principle. The law, which includes the 2053 targets for Turkey and includes a series of measures and implementation methods to achieve significant reductions in carbon emissions, entered into force in the Official Gazette at the beginning of July 2025. This study examines the extent of changes made compared to the norms that entered into force with the Official Gazette and were previously passed by parliament in April 2025 due to considerable debate. It is important to understand how these changes will be amended, particularly in social media, and to avoid misunderstandings based on allegations of major conspiracies. It is argued that claims that these amendments will interfere with individual lives, particularly on social media, should be understood as the provisions of the law addressing the issue solely at the institutions level and with an economic dimension. As a result of the study, recommendations are presented for a better understanding of the law implemented in academic, public, and industrial sectors.

Keywords: Climate Law, Social Media, Public Relations, Labor Economics

Adem KAYAR, PhD, Digital and Sustainable Future Association, Chairman of the Board

ORCID: 0000-0003-3413-128X

The Impact of Digital Transformation in Industry on Circular Economy and Carbon Footprint Reduction in the Manufacturing Sector

ABSTRACT

In the contemporary industrial landscape, digital transformation has become a pivotal tool not only for enhancing the efficiency and flexibility of production processes but also for achieving sustainable development goals. Particularly within the manufacturing sector, the integration of digital technologies facilitates more efficient resource utilization, waste reduction, and the minimization of the environmental impact of production processes. In this context, the intersection of circular economy principles with digital transformation presents significant potential for carbon footprint reduction and the development of sustainable production models.

While there's a growing body of literature on digital transformation and sustainability, comprehensive studies that specifically examine the integrated and tangible effects of digital transformation technologies on the circular economy and carbon footprint reduction within the manufacturing sector, especially in the context of Turkey, remain limited. This study aims to fill this gap by deeply exploring the potential of digital technologies in this domain, with a particular focus on their applications in Turkey. This study elaborates on how digital transformation applications in the Turkish manufacturing sector integrate with the circular economy concept and contribute to the reduction of carbon emissions. The utilization of digital technologies such as the Internet of Things (IoT), big data analytics, artificial intelligence, robotic automation, and energy management systems significantly enhances energy efficiency in production lines, minimizes material waste through process optimization, and consequently enables a reduction in carbon emissions.

Furthermore, in light of the European Union's circular economy and sustainability policies, Turkey's current industrial policies and digitalization strategies are comparatively evaluated. This comparison aims to develop adaptable strategies specific to Turkey. The data-driven analysis and decision support systems provided by digital transformation are critically important for monitoring and improving sustainability performance. In conclusion, digital transformation in industry provides substantial

contributions to the widespread adoption of circular economy practices and the reduction of the carbon footprint within the manufacturing sector. These advancements offer strategic opportunities for both enhancing economic competitiveness and ensuring environmental sustainability. Accordingly, the collaborative efforts of policymakers, industry stakeholders, and technology developers are crucial for the adoption and dissemination of digital transformation-focused sustainable industrial strategies.

Keywords: Carbon footprint, circular economy, industrial digital transformation, smart manufacturing, production systems, sustainability,

SESSION 4 PRESENTATION – Moderated by Betül GÜR, Prof. Dr.

Serap ÖZTÜRK, Manager, Republic of Türkiye Ministry of Agriculture and Forestry, Istanbul/Beyoğlu District Directorate of Agriculture and Forestry, Istanbul/Beyoğlu İlçesi Sürdürülebilirlik Çalışmaları: İyi Uygulama Örnekleri / Istanbul/Beyoğlu District Sustainability Studies: Good Practice Examples

ABSTRACT

This presentation aims to share the objectives, scope, implementation methods and concrete results of the environment-focused projects we are carrying out in our district. The main purpose of these studies is to contribute to the protection of natural resources, improve waste management and raise awareness of sustainability in society. In terms of scope, the aim is to implement environmental transformation projects and to communicate this transformation to different segments of society. Among the projects we have carried out, composting applications aimed at returning food waste to nature are at the forefront. Thanks to this application, organic waste has been recycled in an environmentally friendly manner and the amount of waste has been reduced. Another important initiative is the reuse of ghost nets retrieved from the sea. These nets have been transformed into fashion items such as hats and clothing through collaboration with the Maturation Institute, thereby contributing to the reduction of marine pollution and supporting the circular economy concept. In addition, in collaboration with schools and local authorities in our district, awareness-raising activities have been carried out on food waste conversion, water conservation, rainwater harvesting and urban agriculture. These activities have increased awareness at both the individual and societal levels. In joint projects carried out with ITU Environmental Engineering students, various applications to prevent water waste were developed, and creative solutions for water conservation in public areas were explored. In addition, field studies on urban agriculture were conducted in collaboration with Kasımpaşa Sports Club, and sustainable agriculture practices within the city were supported. As a result of all these efforts, environmental awareness has increased in Beyoğlu, local residents have shown greater interest in sustainable living practices, and the foundations for a participatory

environmental movement have been laid. Environmental responsibility has been strengthened, particularly among younger generations, and Beyoğlu has made exemplary progress towards sustainable urban living.

Keywords: Compost, Urban Agriculture, Food Waste, Ghost Nets, Sustainability

Müge KOÇUM SEVİM, PhD, Visiting Lecturer, İstinye University

ORCID: 0000-0002-0746-6183

Figen YAVUZ, Assist. Prof., İstanbul Nişantaşı University

ORCID: 0000-0002-6701-7961

Tekstil Sektöründe Döngüsel Ekonomi Yaklaşımları: Uygulamalar, Zorluklar ve Gelecek Perspektifleri / Circular Economy Approaches in the Textile Sector: Applications, Challenges and Future Perspectives

ABSTRACT

The textile industry is one of the sectors most in need of applying circular economy principles due to its high environmental impact. The industry, which stands out for its intensive use of water, chemicals and energy in production processes, creates serious waste problems, especially in conjunction with the fast fashion concept. Traditional economic models lead to excessive resource consumption, waste production and environmental degradation, whereas the circular economy aims to extend the life cycle of products, re-evaluate waste without removing it from the system, and protect natural resources. Thus, environmental impacts are minimised at every stage of product design, production, consumption and disposal. This study examines the concept of the circular economy specifically in the textile sector, analysing current practices, challenges encountered, and future perspectives. Practices such as the use of recycled materials, repair services, resale, product collection systems, and closed-loop production are at the forefront of the sector's transformation. However, consumer habits, technological costs, infrastructure deficiencies, and inadequate legal regulations pose significant obstacles to this transformation. Firstly, consumer habits make it difficult to adopt the circular model. The fast fashion culture, which is based on cheap and frequent shopping, creates an obstacle to the preference for high-quality and durable products. The circular economy approach is of critical importance for the sustainability of the textile sector. The circular economy is not only an environmental necessity for the textile sector but also an innovative model that offers economic opportunities. By reducing waste, improving material efficiency, and developing new business models, both the environment and the economy can benefit. Multi-stakeholder collaborations between

academia, policymakers, and industry representatives are essential for the success of this transformation.

Keywords: Circular Economy, Textile Sector, Sustainability, Resource Efficiency

Selda ERDOĞAN, PhD (c), Lecturer, İstanbul Medipol University

ORCID: 0000-0002-5524-8412

Cihat KÖKSAL, Assoc. Prof. İstanbul Ticaret University

ORCID: 0000-0003-4621-7697

Tekstil Sektöründe Döngüsel Ekonomi Yaklaşımları: Uygulamalar, Zorluklar ve Gelecek Perspektifleri / The Effect of Carbon Emission and Ecological Footprint on International Trade: The Case of Textile Sector

ABSTRACT

The rapid increase in the emission of toxic gases such as CO₂ resulting from the use of fossil fuels and industrial activities has plunged the world into a global problem of climate change and global warming, which is becoming increasingly difficult to prevent. To address these and future problems, many organizations and countries, including the European Union, have convened to assess the situation and focused on what needs to be done. Using our conceptual approach, we have reviewed the literature and analyzed using variables such as Carbon Emissions and Ecological Footprints under the Environmental Kuznets Curve Hypothesis. The research discusses measures to be taken for resource sustainability, including carbon emissions and the need for a green transformation for the textile sector, one of the most polluting sectors, and Türkiye's approach to the issue. The research aims to provide important policy recommendations for the textile sector in Türkiye.

Keywords: Ecological Footprint, Carbon Emissions, Textile Sector, Environmental Kuznets Curve Hypothesis

Rana Yaren ÖZLÜK, Independent Researcher, Türkiye

ORCID: 0009-0006-2373-7205

Döngüsel Ekonomiye Geçişte Türkiye Tekstil Sektörü Uygulamaları / Turkish Textile Sector Practices in Transition to Circular Economy

ABSTRACT

This study emphasizes the need to address structural changes in traditional production and consumption systems with a sense of urgency, and uses qualitative research methods to examine applications developed in the Türkiye textile sector, which is a major consumer of water and energy, to promote this awareness. While discussing waste management practices within the scope of the Zero Waste Project, it was observed that industrial symbiosis, one of the important business models in the circular economy, provides resource efficiency and cooperation in waste-free industrial production. The value of second-hand textile markets, another application, was emphasized in terms of sustainability. The current understanding of fashion is based on fast consumption, which leads to high levels of waste and environmental pollution during production and after consumption. One of the applications developed under the Zero Waste Project to prevent this pollution is the establishment of second-hand textile collection systems. The system enables the transportation of products to reuse and recycling facilities by placing textile waste in public areas by metropolitan municipalities, while also providing opportunities for citizens in need of social assistance to benefit from it. Türkiye has successful projects in the industrial symbiosis business model, which maximizes resource efficiency and supports sector collaboration. The fact that the investments made as a result of the project will be amortized within 1-2 years is an incentive for investment in this area. While current applications are considered a positive start, the need for systematic and technology-based strategies covering the entire sector should not be overlooked. The aim should be to make applications effective and widespread throughout the country with the support of legal regulations and cooperation between stakeholders. Circular economy applications are of great importance in order to protect the well-being of future generations and leave them a livable world.

Keywords: Sustainability in Production, Textile Sector, Circular Economy, Industrial Symbiosis.

Mehmet DUMAN, Independent Researcher, Türkiye

ORCID: 0009-0005-5408-4160

Türkiye'de Kamu Gözetimi Kurumunun Sürdürülebilirlik Politikaları Üzerindeki Etkisi / The Impact of Public Oversight on Sustainability Policies in Türkiye

ABSTRACT

The climate crisis stands as one of the most far-reaching environmental threats faced by the human family, with its impacts extending well beyond ecosystems into economic, social, and political domains. The management of this global challenge has necessitated a comprehensive international effort, and in this regard, the United Nations Framework Convention on Climate Change (UNFCCC), adopted in 1992, laid the first institutional foundation for global climate governance. This process has since been formalized and deepened through numerous international agreements, protocols, and obligations imposed on signatory states. Within this context, the concept of sustainable development has emerged as a fundamental approach to understanding and addressing the long-term and multidimensional nature of the climate crisis. Sustainability's holistic structure—which encompasses not only environmental concerns but also economic and social balance—has rendered it a strategic tool in efforts to mitigate the effects of the crisis. As both a member of the United Nations and a country engaged in the harmonization process with the European Union, Turkey has placed institutional emphasis on climate policy and undertaken responsibilities through various public authorities. This study focuses on the contribution of the Public Oversight Authority (POA), which published the Türkiye Sustainability Reporting Standards (TSRS) in 2023, to Turkey's climate policy framework. The analysis addresses how the institution, through its sustainability-centered regulations, has provided structural support to both national climate efforts and the alignment with international norms. Methodologically, this research is based on data collection and follows a qualitative research approach through document analysis. The findings indicate that the POA has made a meaningful institutional contribution to Turkey's climate action through sustainability reporting, and that it has established itself as an influential actor in guiding the private sector in this domain

Keywords: climate crisis, POA, sustainability, TSRS

Türkiye Döngüsel Ekonomi Politikaları
Sıfır Atık

Atık miktarını azaltarak bu atıklar için toplama sistemlerinin verimli işleyişini sağlamak ve işlem sonucunda da toplanan atıkların geri dönüştürülmesini hedefleyen sistem tehditleri minimize etmek veya yok etmek istemektedir.

FINAL CONFERENCE
28 July 2025

Rana Yaren Özlük

Abdul Nabyev, Esra Tamer, Şeyma Koçyiğit, Mariam Tedora..., Nejat Özden, Sadia Ayaz, Rida zahara

CLOSING STATEMENT – Declared by Prof. Dr. Betül GÜR, Chair Holder

Today, we have gathered here to hold the closing event of our Jean Monnet Chair for EU's Circular Economy Policies and Sustainability. As always, we were joined by a wonderful group of participants. We listened to valuable presentations. Our distinguished participants followed the sessions with great interest.

Although we are closing the Jean Monnet Chair for CESPEU today, interest in circularity and sustainability is actually growing. Academic studies and projects are being carried out in every field of science related to economic, political and social life, and a rich literature is emerging.

Indeed, the emergence of new powers within the transformation process of the global economy and politics today underscores the importance of circular economy and sustainability policies. The EU's policies aimed at production and export within the framework of sustainable and circular economy principles are pushing both global production and trade, as well as emerging new economies that are competing with it, to develop new economic and political strategies.

Therefore, circular economy and sustainability policies are emerging as important factors that will shape the economic and environmental landscape of the future. Jean Monnet is primarily a teaching and educational activity. We also started with courses and theses within this framework. Over the course of three years, we offered courses on European Economic Integration, Industrial Policies, Advanced Industrial Policies, Seminars, the Multilateral Trade System, the Circular Economy, and Sustainability within the Chair framework. These courses were taught in both Turkish and English at the undergraduate, master's, and

Bugün burada Döngüsel Ekonomi Politikaları ve Sürdürülebilirlik Jean Monnet Kürsümüzün, kapanış etkinliğini gerçekleştirmek üzere toplandık. Her zamanki gibi güzel bir katılımcı grubu bugün de bizi yalnız bırakmadı. Birbirinden kıymetli sunumlar dinledik. Birbirinden kıymetli katılımcılarımız ilgiyle oturumları takip etti.

Biz bugün her ne kadar Jean Monnet Chair'ı kapatıyor olsak da, aslında Döngüsellik ve Sürdürülebilirlik konularına duyulan ilgili giderek artmakta.. İktisadi, siyasi, toplumsal hayata ilişkin, bilim dünyasının her alanında bu konuda akademik çalışmalar, projeler yapılmakta ve zengin bir literatür oluşmaktadır. Zira günümüzde küresel ekonominin ve siyasetin dönüşüm süreci içinde yeni güçlerin ortaya çıkması, döngüsel ekonomi ve sürdürülebilirlik politikalarının önemini daha da vurgulamaktadır. AB'nin sürdürülebilir ve döngüsel ekonomi ilkeleri çerçevesinde üretim ve ihracat yapmaya yönelik politikaları gerek küresel üretim ve ticareti, gerekse kendisine rakip yükselen yeni ekonomileri iktisadi ve siyasi olarak yeni stratejiler üretmeye itmektedir. Dolayısıyla döngüsel ekonomi ve sürdürülebilirlik politikaları geleceğin ekonomik ve çevresel zeminini belirleyen önemli birer unsur olarak karşımıza çıkmaktadır. Biz de İstanbul Ticaret Üniversitesi olarak konunun bu önemine binaen Avrupa Birliği Döngüsel Ekonomi Politikaları ve Sürdürülebilirlik Jean Monnet Chair olarak AB'nin ekonomik entegrasyonu ve dönüşümü, sanayi politikaları, sürdürülebilirlik ve döngüsel ekonomi politikaları hakkında farkındalığı artırmak ve araştırmaları teşvik etmek amacıyla 3 yıl süren bir yol yürüdük.

doctoral levels. Approximately 330 students took these courses and received certification over the three-year period. Therefore, under the Jean Monnet Chair for CESPEU, with our undergraduate, master's, and doctoral courses, nearly 30 completed and ongoing master's and doctoral theses, and an equal number of postgraduate students' article studies, articles and book chapters co-authored with our postgraduate students and many researchers and academics from both domestic and international institutions interested in the subject, through our newsletters, social media posts, campaigns and social events organised with our students, seminars, workshops, winter and summer schools, and programmes and articles in the written and visual press, we have sought to contribute to the literature and social awareness.

Excluding lectures, approximately 150 distinguished scientists, academics, researchers, civil society and industry representatives presented papers, gave lectures, moderated discussions, wrote articles and book chapters... In other words, they were the ones who taught and shared their knowledge.

Excluding lectures, approximately 150 distinguished scientists, academics, researchers, civil society and industry representatives presented papers, gave lectures, moderated discussions, wrote articles and book chapters, and otherwise contributed to the Chair's activities.

We reached approximately 1,000 distinguished participants in these events. They were the ones who learned, asked questions, shared their knowledge through their interpretations and questions, expressed themselves, but never left us, always staying by our side.

Kürsü olarak üç yıl boyunca lisans, yüksek lisans ve doktora öğrencilerine, akademisyenlere, araştırmacılara ve kamuoyuna yönelik pek çok faaliyet gerçekleştirdik: Jean Monnet öncelikle bir ders verme, bir eğitim-öğretim faaliyetidir. Biz de bu çerçevede ilk olarak dersler ve tezlerle başladık. Üç yıl boyunca her sene Kürsü kapsamında; Avrupa Ekonomik Entegrasyonu, Sanayi Politikaları, İleri Sanayi Politikaları, Seminer, Çok Taraflı Ticaret Sistemi, Döngüsel Ekonomi ve Sürdürülebilirlik derslerini, lisans, yüksek lisans ve doktora hem Türkçe hem de İngilizce olarak verdik. Bu kapsamda 3 yılda yaklaşık 330 öğrenci bu dersleri aldı ve sertifikalandırıldı.

Dolayısıyla Jean Monnet Kürsüsü altında lisans, yüksek lisans ve doktora derslerimizle, tamamlanmış ve tamamlanmak üzere olan 30'a yakın yüksek lisans ve doktora tezlerimizle ve bir o kadar lisansüstü öğrencilerimizin makale çalışmalarlarıyla, lisansüstü öğrencilerimizin ve konuyla ilgilenen yurtiçi ve yurt dışından birçok araştırmacı ve akademisyenle birlikte yazdığımız makaleler ve kitap bölümleriyle, yayınladığımız haber bültenleriyle, sosyal medya paylaşımlarımızla, öğrencilerimizle birlikte düzenlediğimiz kampanyalar ve sosyal etkinliklerle, düzenlediğimiz seminerler, workshoplar, kış okulu ve yaz okulu gibi etkinliklerle, yazılı ve görsel basında gerçekleştirdiğimiz programlar ve haberlerle literatüre ve toplumsal farkındalığa katkı sunmaya çalıştık. Dersler hariç, Chair kapsamındaki etkinliklerde yaklaşık 150 kıymetli bilim insanı, akademisyen, araştırmacı, sivil toplum ve sektör temsilcisi bildiri sundu, ders anlattı, moderasyon yaptı, makale, kitap bölümü yazdı... Yani anlatan, öğreten oldu.

On the other hand, when we consider those who did not physically participate in our events, we actually reached a much larger audience through our news and programmes in the written and visual media, our news bulletins, and our social media posts.

We have not only ensured that today's generations are knowledgeable and aware of circular economy and sustainability policies, but we have also contributed to the training of researchers and future generations who are conscious of these sustainability principles and goals through the courses, theses, and academic studies we have conducted with undergraduate and graduate students. In this context, we have also made a significant contribution to our country's human capital as a Chair.

Throughout this process, we have collaborated with universities both domestically and internationally, and as a result, we have had participants from academia, particularly from the Turkish Republic Ministry of Foreign Affairs, Ministry of Trade, Ministry of Environment, Urbanisation and Climate Change, and Ministry of Agriculture and Forestry, as well as from the public sector, private sector, civil society organisations, and indeed from all walks of life and at all levels. As the Jean Monnet Chair, I would like to thank all our guests and you, our valued audience, for your interest and participation, just as we have done in all our previous events.

As Chair of the Jean Monnet Chair for EU's Circular Economy Policies and Sustainability, I would like to thank our esteemed members Prof. Dr. Elçin AYKAÇ ALP and Assoc. Prof. Dr. Sabri ÖZ for their efforts. I would also like to thank our valued team members, Expert Güllü BUZUNOĞLU, student assistants Rimon AHMED, Aslıgül DEMİREL and Sayed Abdul Kerim

Bu etkinliklerde fiili olarak yaklaşık 1000 kıymetli katılımcıya hitap ettik. Öğrenen, soran, kendi bilgilerini yorumlarıyla ve sorularıyla aktaran, dile getiren ama bizleri hiç bırakmayan, hep yanımızda olan oldular. Öte yandan fiili olarak etkinliklerimize katılmaksızın düşündüğümüzde ise yazılı ve görsel basındaki haberlerimiz ve programlarımızla, haber bültenlerimizle ve Sosyal medya paylaşımlarımızla birlikte değerlendirdiğimizde esasen aslında çok daha büyük bir kitleye hitap etmiş olduk.

Hem halihazırda bugünkü kuşakların döngüsel ekonomi ve sürdürülebilirlik politikalarına ilişkin bilgi sahibi olmalarını ve farkındalığını sağladık, hem de bu sürdürülebilir kalkınma amaçları doğrultusunda, sürdürülebilirlik ilkeleri çerçevesinde, bu bilince sahip araştırmacıların ve gelecek kuşakların yetiştirilmesine lisans ve lisansüstü öğrencilerle birlikte yürüttüğümüz dersler, tezler, akademik çalışmalar sayesinde katkı sunduk. Bu çerçevede ülkemizin beşeri sermayesine biz de Chair olarak önemli bir katkı sağlamış olduk. Bu süreçte yurtiçinden ve yurtdışından üniversitelerle yaptığımız işbirlikleri dolayısıyla akademiden, özellikle Türkiye Cumhuriyeti Dışişleri Bakanlığı, Ticaret Bakanlığı, Çevre Şehircilik ve İklim Değişikliği Bakanlığı ve Tarım ve Orman Bakanlığı gibi kamudan, özel sektörden, sivil toplum kuruluşlarından, hasılı her kesimden ve her düzeyde katılımcı bizlerle oldu. Jean Monnet Chair olarak bugüne kadarki etkinliklerimizde olduğu gibi, bugün de aramızda olan bütün misafirlerimize ve siz kıymetli haziruna ilginiz ve katılımınız için teşekkür ediyorum. AB Döngüsel Ekonomi Politikaları ve Sürdürülebilirlik Jean Monnet Kürsüsü Başkanı olarak Kürsümüzün kıymetli üyeleri Prof. Dr. Elçin AYKAÇ ALP ve Doç. Dr. Sabri ÖZ'e emekleri için teşekkür ederim.

HAQIQ, who joined our team and supported us with their dedicated work.

Our activities were so intense that there were times when even our team could not keep up. It was precisely at this point that our beloved students, who did not leave their professors alone, volunteered to take on active roles in various stages of our activities, thereby gaining many skills and competencies beyond scientific knowledge. In this regard, I would like to thank the highly valued, brilliant master's and doctoral students of Industrial Policies and Technology Management the master's students in Digital Economy and Marketing, the undergraduate students in the Economics Department of the Faculty of Business Administration, the master's students in Economics, the undergraduate students in the International Trade Department of the Faculty of Business Administration, and the Economics Society, the student club of the Economics Department at İstanbul Ticaret University. They took courses under the Jean Monnet Chair for CESPEU, and sometimes attended events as listeners, sometimes asked questions, sometimes made comments, and sometimes took part in the organisation of our face-to-face events. Sometimes in the intense debates they organised over weeks, and sometimes in the EU Heads of State and Government Summit Simulation they conducted, they all took on the role of the head of state of an EU member country and discussed the EU's sustainability and circular economy policies in the context of current global developments. In short, looking back over the three years of our activities under the Jean Monnet Chair, we have all been both students and teachers to one another. We have learned from each other and taught each other.

3 kişi olarak başladığımız bu yolda ekibimize katılarak bizlere özverili çalışmalarıyla destek olan kıymetli ekip arkadaşlarımız Uzman Güllü BUZUNOĞLU, öğrenci asistanlarımız Rimon AHMED, Aslıgül DEMİREL ve Sayed Abdul Kerim HAQIQ'e de teşekkür ederim. Öyle yoğun geçti ki etkinliklerimiz, ekip olarak bile yetişemediğimiz zamanlar da oldu. İşte tam da bu sırada biz hocalarını yalnız bırakmayan, gönüllü olarak etkinliklerimizin çeşitli aşamalarında aktif görevler almaya talip olarak, aslında kendileri de bu şekilde bilimsel bilginin dışında pekçok beceri ve yetkinlik kazanan çok sevgili öğrencilerimiz oldu.

Bu itibarla İstanbul Ticaret Üniversitesi'nin birbirinden değerli, pırl pırl Sanayi Politikaları ve Teknoloji Yönetimi yüksek lisans ve doktora öğrencilerine, Dijital Ekonomi ve Pazarlama yüksek lisans öğrencilerine, İşletme Fakültesi İktisat Bölümü lisans öğrencilerine, İktisat yüksek lisans öğrencilerine, İşletme Fakültesi Uluslararası Ticaret Bölümü lisans öğrencilerine, İktisat bölümünün öğrenci kulübü olan Ekonomi Topluluğu'na ayrıca teşekkür ederim. Hem Jean Monnet Chair kapsamındaki dersleri aldılar, hem etkinlikler de bazen dinleyici oldular, bazen soru sordular, bazen yorum yaptılar, bazen yüzyüze düzenlediğimiz etkinliklerimizin organizasyonlarımızda görev aldılar.

Bazen haftalarca düzenledikleri kıyasıya Münazaralarda, bazen de gerçekleştirdikleri AB Devlet ve Hükümet Başkanları Zirvesi Simülasyonu'nda hepsi birer AB üyesi ülkenin devlet başkanı rolünü üstlenip ABnin Sürdürülebilirlik ve Döngüsel Ekonomi politikalarını güncel küresel gelişmeler çerçevesinde tartıştılar,

Essentially, I do not see this conference or this speech as a conclusion. On the contrary, I see the Jean Monnet Chair for EU's Circular Economy Policies and Sustainability, as well as the collaborations and friendships we have established during this process, as an opportunity to launch new projects and collaborations that will contribute to both academia and society.

On behalf of myself as the Chair of the Jean Monnet Chair, as well as our esteemed members Prof. Dr. Elçin AYKAÇ ALP and Assoc. Prof. Dr. Sabri ÖZ, and our valued team members Expert Güllü BUZUNOĞLU, assistants Rimon AHMED, Aslıgül DEMİREL, and Sayed Abdul Kerim HAQIQ, I would like to thank everyone and extend **my regards**.

Hasılı, Jean Monnet Chair 3 yıl boyunca süren etkinliklerimiz süresince katılım gösteren herkes için geriye dönüp baktığımızda birbirimizin hem öğrencisi hem hocası olmuşuz. Hep beraber birbirimizden hem öğrendik, hem de öğrettik. Esasen bu konferansı, bu konuşmayı bir kapanış olarak görmüyorum. Bilakis AB Döngüsel Ekonomi Politikaları ve Sürdürülebilirlik Jean Monnet Kürsüsü'nü ve bu süreç içinde kurduğumuz işbirliklerini ve dostlukları birer vesile olarak kabul ediyor, beraberce içinde yer alacağımız, hem akademiye hem de topluma katkı sunan yeni projelerin, yeni işbirliklerinin bir başlangıcı olarak görüyorum. Gerek Jean Monnet Kürsüsü Başkanı olarak şahsım adına, gerekse Kürsümüzün kıymetli üyeleri Prof. Dr. Elçin AYKAÇ ALP ve Doç. Dr. Sabri ÖZ ile kıymetli ekip arkadaşlarımız Uzman Güllü BUZUNOĞLU, asistanlarımız Rimon AHMED, Aslıgül DEMİREL ve Sayed Abdul Kerim HAQIQ adına, herkese teşekkür ediyor, **saygılar sunuyorum**.

